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D7.5 – Policy guidelines aimed at different levels of governance, supported by evidence-based adaptation planning tools and use scenarios

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
API	Application Programming Interface
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
CCLL	Coastal City Living Lab
DT-EWS	Digital Twin and Early Warning System
EBA	Ecosystem-based Adaptation
ECFAS	European Coastal Flood Awareness System
EU	European Union
EWS	Early-Warning Support
ICLEI	International Council for Local Environmental Initiatives
ICZM	Integrated Coastal Zone Management
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LLs	Living Labs
MCA	Multi-Criteria Analysis
MOOC	Massive Open Online Courses
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
Nbs	Nature-based solutions
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
SIP	Smart Integrated Platform
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SOS	Sensor Observation Service
UNFCCC	UN Framework Convention on Climate Change
USE	User Scenario Evaluation
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WP	Work Package

BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE SCORE PROJECT

SCORE is a four-year EU-funded project aiming to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities.

The intensification of extreme weather events, coastal erosion and sea-level rise are major challenges to be urgently addressed by European coastal cities. The science behind these disruptive phenomena is complex, and advancing climate resilience requires progress in data acquisition, forecasting, and understanding of the potential risks and impacts for real-scenario interventions. The Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) supported by smart technologies has potential to increase climate resilience of European coastal cities; however, it is not yet adequately understood and coordinated at European level.

To fill this gap, SCORE outlines a co-creation strategy, developed via a network of 10 coastal city 'living labs' (CCLs), to rapidly, equitably and sustainably enhance coastal city climate resilience through EBAs and sophisticated digital technologies.

The 10 coastal city living labs involved in the project are: Sligo and Dublin, Ireland; Barcelona/Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm and Oarsoaldea, Spain; Oeiras, Portugal; Massa, Italy; Piran, Slovenia; Gdansk, Poland; Samsun, Turkey.

SCORE will establish an integrated coastal zone management (ICZM) framework for strengthening EBA and smart coastal city policies, creating European leadership in coastal city climate change adaptation in line with the Paris Agreement. It will provide innovative platforms to empower stakeholders' deployment of EBAs to increase climate resilience, business opportunities and financial sustainability of coastal cities.

The SCORE interdisciplinary team consists of 28 world-leading organisations from academia, local authorities, RPOs, and SMEs encompassing a wide range of skills including environmental science and policy, climate modelling, citizen and social science, data management, coastal management and engineering, security and technological aspects of smart sensing research.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the SCORE project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534. It presents a concise set of policy recommendations grounded in SCORE's extensive research, pilot implementation, and stakeholder collaboration across ten Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs).

The recommendations target policymakers at local, national, and EU levels, offering practical guidance to support the integration of ecosystem-based adaptation (EBA) measures, participatory planning, the living lab concept, and innovative technical and financial tools into policy and planning processes across a variety of coastal management contexts. These policy insights are designed to align with and reinforce existing frameworks such as the EU Climate Change Adaptation Strategy, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), the Floods Directive, the Water Framework Directive, the EU Biodiversity Strategy, and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Importantly, the guidelines contain evidence on coastal ecosystem services and their adaptation costs and benefits, as these have emerged from the SCORE project's extensive work, especially its success stories. They demonstrate how public value is created through the adaptation measures designed and implemented in SCORE, providing actionable guidance on how such measures can be supported and integrated at various governance levels, from local and regional to European.

Through evidence-based recommendations and tested practices, this deliverable supports public authorities, policymakers, and other stakeholders in enhancing their coastal climate resilience strategies, while enabling the wider uptake and replication of SCORE's integrated approach across Europe.

LINKS WITH OTHER PROJECT ACTIVITIES

This deliverable is the culmination of an integrated effort across the SCORE project's work packages, each of which has contributed foundational insights, tools, and tested methodologies that have been translated into actionable policy recommendations. The research outputs, technological innovations, and community-based experiences generated across the WPs on assessing climate risks (WP1), designing and implementing living labs (WP2), collecting data, downscaling and modelling (WP3), adopting participatory and citizen science approaches (WP4), designing IT solutions like the ICT platform (WP5) and the digital twin (WP8), developing financial resilience tools (WP6), performing socio-economic assessment of EBA measures (WP7) and carrying out communication and capacity building practices (WP9) have all directly informed the structure and substance of these guidelines. As such, this deliverable represents a shared output of the entire consortium, transforming SCORE's interdisciplinary research and practice into practical guidance for climate-resilient governance.

CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	8
2. DEFINITION OF TERMS	10
3. TARGET AUDIENCE	11
4. ADDRESSING GAPS IN POLICY IMPLEMENTATION	14
4.1. EU Policy	14
4.1.1 Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)	14
4.1.2 Water Framework Directive (WFD)	16
4.1.3 Flood Directive	18
4.1.4 EU Nature Directives (Birds, Habitats, Natura sites)	20
4.1.5 Biodiversity Strategy	22
4.1.6 EU Climate Change Adaptation Strategy	24
4.2. International Policy	29
4.2.1 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	29
4.2.2 Paris Agreement	32
5. POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS	35
5.1. Introduction	35
5.2. Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA)	37
5.2.1 Description of outputs and tools	37
5.2.2. Recommendations at different levels	41
5.3 Coastal Cities Living Labs (CCLLs)	44
5.3.1 Description of outputs and tools	44
5.3.2. Recommendations at different levels	46
5.4 Participatory and Citizen Science Approaches	49
5.4.1 Description of outputs and tools	49
5.4.2. Recommendations at different levels	51
5.5 Financial Resilience and Risk Management Tools	54
5.5.1 Description of outputs and tools	54
5.5.2. Recommendations at different levels	57
5.6 Data collection, downscaling and modelling	60
5.6.1 Description of outputs and tools	60
5.6.2. Recommendations at different levels	61
5.7 IT Solutions	64
5.7.1 Description of outputs and tools	64
5.7.2. Recommendations at different levels	66
5.8 Educational, Communicational, and Capacity-Building Tools	69
5.8.1 Description of outputs and tools	69
5.8.2. Recommendations at different levels	70
6. SYSTEMIC ADOPTION OF LIVING LABS	72
7. COMPLEMENTARITIES OF SCORE WITH ECFAS	74
8. FEW SUCCESS STORIES FROM CCLLs ADAPTATION MEASURES	76
9. BUSINESS OPPORTUNITIES	80

10. OTHER SCORE POLICY GUIDELINES	81
11. FOLLOW-UP ACTION PLAN	82
12. REFERENCES.....	83
13. RESOURCES.....	84

TABLES

Table 1: List of SCORE target groups	13
Table 2: SCORE outputs and tools	35
Table 3: Governance levels.....	36

1. INTRODUCTION

The SCORE project conducted applied research across ten European coastal cities through the establishment of Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs), focusing on co-creating and testing ecosystem-based adaptation (EBA) measures. It combined digital tools, citizen science, and socio-economic analysis to assess climate risks and support evidence-based urban resilience planning.

The objective of this deliverable is to translate those research results into actionable policy recommendations, enabling those in positions of influence to make informed decisions and drive long-term climate resilience in European coastal cities.

The document is designed to provide policymakers with a clear and practical overview of the SCORE project's contributions to enhancing coastal climate resilience. It begins by identifying and describing the target audience for the policy recommendations, establishing who these recommendations are intended to support across local, national, and EU levels. It then continues with an overview of the main EU and international policy directives and strategies relevant to coastal adaptation summarizing each policy's scope, key initiatives, existing gaps, and how SCORE outputs align with and can help address these challenges.

The core of the deliverable is devoted to the description of the outputs and tools developed within the SCORE project, grouped by seven thematic categories, each accompanied by specific policy recommendations for their integration into decision-making frameworks at different governance levels.

Each thematic category reflects a comprehensive approach to enhancing climate resilience in European coastal cities. The project's contributions include the socio-economic assessment of ecosystem-based adaptation (EBA) options through cost-benefit and multi-criteria analyses, complemented by an extensive EBA Catalogue. The CCLL framework, along with co-creation toolkits, pilot operational plans, evaluation and monitoring frameworks, underpins participatory adaptation strategies. Participatory and citizen science initiatives, including platforms for geospatial data collection, low-cost sensor catalogues, a citizen science playbook, geodesign games, and frameworks, have empowered local communities and stakeholders. Financial resilience and risk management tools, such as methodologies for climate risk assessment, quantitative risk profiles, and decision support systems, equip cities to manage residual risks effectively. Data collection efforts, including hazard flooding maps and coastal erosion analyses, are integrated with advanced IT solutions like the SCORE ICT platform and Digital Twin technology, providing real-time decision support. Finally, educational and capacity-building initiatives, including Massive Open Online Courses, webinars, training schools, and interactive workshops, have broadened awareness and built resilience capacity across the participating regions. These interconnected outputs exemplify SCORE's holistic approach to coastal climate resilience and provide a solid evidence base for the project's policy recommendations.

The document also includes a brief description of the complementarity of SCORE and the European Coastal Flood Awareness System (ECFAS¹), followed by success stories from SCORE's CCLLs that showcase real-world applications of adaptation measures. It also highlights emerging business opportunities enabled by SCORE tools and approaches. Finally, a follow-up action plan is suggested to ensure ongoing engagement with policymakers and to support the long-term integration of SCORE's results into climate adaptation policy and planning processes.

¹ <https://www.ecfas.eu/>

Embedding the research outcomes into local, national, and EU policy frameworks is not only essential for enhancing resilience in coastal cities, but also for scaling successful strategies and ensuring systemic transformation toward climate-resilient urban futures.

2. DEFINITION OF TERMS

Definition of adaptation to climate change

Adaptation is the process of adjustment to actual or expected climate and its effects. In human systems, adaptation seeks to moderate or avoid harm or exploit beneficial opportunities. In some natural systems, human intervention may facilitate adjustment to expected climate and its effects (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, IPCC 2018). Adaptation can take various forms and operate at multiple scales, ranging from local to national and international levels.

While EBAs are an essential subset, leveraging biodiversity and ecosystem services for adaptation, adaptation also includes a broader spectrum of actions, such as:

- **Technical Measures:** Engineering solutions like sea walls, flood barriers, or upgraded urban drainage systems to reduce vulnerability to extreme weather events.
- **Educational Initiatives:** Public awareness campaigns and capacity-building programs to foster understanding and behavioral change.
- **Institutional and Policy Reforms:** Establishing regulations, land-use planning frameworks, and financial mechanisms to embed climate resilience into decision-making processes at all governance levels.

This integrated approach is supported by the Paris Agreement (UNFCCC, 2015) and further elaborated in the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report (IPCC, 2022), which highlights the necessity of combining nature-based, technical, social, and institutional interventions to build systemic resilience.

Clarification in the use of the terms NbS and EBA within the text

EBA first emerged in 2008 during the United Nations Framework Convention for Climate Change (UNFCCC) (Wertz-Kanounnikoff et al., 2011). EBA refer to "an integrative approach combining biodiversity and ecosystem services within climate change adaptation planning to promote urban capacities to adapt to climate change" (adapted from the Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity, 2009).

Recently, EBA – alongside other related concepts, such as green infrastructure and ecosystem services, have been categorized under the umbrella term of nature-based solutions or NbS (Nesshöver et al., 2017; Pauleit et al., 2017; Naumann et al., 2011). NbS was introduced by the World Bank and the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) towards the end of the 2000s as "Actions to protect, manage and restore natural or modified ecosystems, which address societal challenges, effectively and adaptively, providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits".

Both terms will be used in this deliverable, either to refer to the implementation of nature-based measures targeting exclusively climate change adaptation or broader goals (e.g., human health, social inclusion, biodiversity conservation, etc.).

3. TARGET AUDIENCE

The consortium has identified several groups with a stake in or likely to be impacted by the SCORE project (also mentioned in Section 2.2 of D9.1 Dissemination Plan²). Table 1 outlines the key target groups most relevant to the SCORE policy recommendations (core group), as well as those that are less central but still relevant (secondary group). It also provides the rationale for engaging each group and the proposed approach to influence their decision-making.

Target group	Description of target group	Relevance	Purpose
Government bodies and policy makers (core group)	This broad group includes local, regional, and national authorities, representatives and associations, ministries, parliaments, and national, and international public administrations.	They define regulations, national policies, and funding frameworks.	To inform policy formulation and regulatory updates with robust scientific and local evidence from our work in CCLs. Our goal is to advocate for systemic changes using EBA, participatory and data-informed strategies.
EU Policymakers (core group)	This group includes officials and representatives from the European Commission, European Parliament, European Council, EU agencies, and key Directorates-General (e.g. DG CLIMA, DG ENV, DG REGIO) responsible for shaping and implementing EU-level climate, environmental, and regional development policies.	EU policymakers play a central role in framing the legislative, regulatory, and funding environment for climate resilience across Member States. Their decisions influence national and local adaptation strategies, research agendas, and the alignment of cross-border climate action.	To ensure that SCORE policy recommendations inform future EU strategies, directives, and funding programmes, especially under the European Green Deal, Mission Adaptation, and Cohesion Policy.
Coastal Cities (core group)	Targets all the important political and technical actors in European coastal cities: Policy/Governance: Chambers of Commerce, City	They are the primary users and implementers of climate resilience strategies. They can be the direct users of SCORE outputs such as hazard maps, early warning	To guide local policy decisions, urban planning, and community engagement initiatives. We intend to empower them

² <https://zenodo.org/records/11242969>

	<p>Councils, local / regional politicians</p> <p>Communities: general public, local citizens</p> <p>Housing, planning authorities</p>	<p>systems, sensors for citizen science etc.</p>	<p>with practical, evidence-based recommendations that can shape climate adaptation plans and citizen involvement.</p>
<p>Academic and “Research and Development” community (secondary group)</p>	<p>All research communities interested in the project's developments, results, and innovations that could benefit their own research activities. This includes climate model experts, climate scientists, environmental scientists, engineers, social scientists, and others.</p>	<p>Their work benefits from cutting-edge data, models, and innovative approaches, such as risk modelling, CCLL methodology, digital twins etc.</p>	<p>Influence future research agendas and climate resilience frameworks and integrate SCORE outcomes into academic discourse and further innovation cycles.</p>
<p>Industrial sector (secondary group)</p>	<p>Organizations, companies and SMEs in various sectors:</p> <p>Climate technology, weather station / sensor manufacturers, software developers</p> <p>Civil Engineers, city planners</p> <p>Insurance companies</p>	<p>Innovation in climate technologies, planning, and insurance is essential for implementation and upscaling.</p>	<p>To stimulate market-driven solutions and influence product/service development in alignment with SCORE outcomes. We aim to encourage public-private partnerships (PPPs) and the adoption of new tools.</p>
<p>European and international networks and European Technology clusters (secondary group)</p>	<p>This group refers to activities addressing external task forces and relevant European technology clusters.</p>	<p>They amplify innovation, foster cross-sector synergies, and scale up successful practices.</p>	<p>To influence technology roadmaps and promote SCORE innovations at a strategic European level. To promote scaling and standardization of tools like the ICT platform and Digital Twin.</p>
<p>EU projects and networks working in similar domain</p>	<p>The participation of project partners in other relevant projects offers the opportunity to establish</p>	<p>They share common goals and face similar challenges.</p>	<p>To foster cross-project learning, co-develop recommendations,</p>

(secondary group)	quick links among parties through joint actions.		and increase outreach.
General public (secondary group)	General public consists of a general audience and other actors not identified as direct targeted groups by the project, though this group can have strong interest in the project: citizen Interest Groups, NGOs, Community Action Groups, students, etc.	Public understanding and support are critical for democratic legitimacy and societal resilience.	To influence behaviour, raise awareness, and promote bottom-up pressure for policy implementation. We are simplifying key messages and make them accessible to all societal groups through MOOCs, community workshops, gamified tools, open-access platforms and citizen science actions.

Table 1: List of SCORE target groups

4.ADDRESSING GAPS IN POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

Below is an overview of key policies and directives addressing climate change, biodiversity, water management, and disaster resilience. This section highlights gaps in their implementation and explores how SCORE outputs can help bridge these gaps.

4.1. EU Policy

4.1.1 Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)

(a) Short Description of the Policy³

The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (2008/56/EC) is the EU's main legislative instrument for the protection of the marine environment. Its objective is to achieve or maintain Good Environmental Status (GES) of all EU marine waters by applying an ecosystem-based approach to the management of human activities. Adopted in 2008, the directive sets out a framework for Member States to assess, monitor, and reduce the impact of human pressures on the marine environment.

The MSFD requires Member States to develop marine strategies that include: (a) initial assessment of marine waters; (b) definition of GES across 11 descriptors (e.g. biodiversity, sea-floor integrity, contaminants, noise); (c) monitoring programs, and (d) programmes of measures to achieve GES.

It also promotes coordination between countries sharing marine regions and integrates with other EU legislation such as the Water Framework Directive and the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive.

In recent years, the MSFD has been reinforced by new initiatives and legislative developments. In 2023, the European Commission completed its review of the directive as part of broader efforts under the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 to enhance marine ecosystem protection and restoration. That same year, the Commission also published an assessment of the marine monitoring programmes reported by Member States, identifying strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement.

The third cycle of implementation began in 2024, during which Member States are expected to review and update their marine strategies and programmes of measures. The Commission is also in the process of assessing the outcomes of the second implementation cycle (2018–2023).

Importantly, the EU Nature Restoration Law, adopted in 2024, sets legally binding, time-bound targets for the restoration of marine habitats and species, including many that fall under the scope of the MSFD and regional sea conventions. This law strengthens the MSFD's environmental objectives by embedding them in enforceable restoration targets.

³ environment.ec.europa.eu

(b) Key Initiatives in Support of the Policy

Several EU funding instruments and strategic initiatives actively support the implementation of MSFD. These can be grouped into the following categories:

Research and innovation programmes: Horizon Europe plays a central role by funding scientific research and innovation relevant to marine monitoring, climate resilience, and ecosystem-based management. It promotes data-driven approaches and technologies such as digital twins and citizen science. The LIFE and PRIMA programmes also support targeted actions on water quality, biodiversity conservation, and pollution control in marine areas.

Marine and regional development funding: The European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF) supports sustainable marine resource use and ecosystem restoration. Complementary funding comes from the European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF), including the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and the Cohesion Fund, which co-finance monitoring systems, infrastructure, and cross-regional cooperation aligned with MSFD objectives.

External action and data infrastructure: Beyond the EU's internal funding, external instruments like the Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument (NDICI – Global Europe) and the Partnership Instrument facilitate marine cooperation in neighbouring seas and with non-EU countries. Meanwhile, initiatives like the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS), the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet), and the INSPIRE Directive provide essential marine data, interoperability frameworks, and infrastructure to support monitoring and reporting under the MSFD.

(c) Relation with the SCORE Project

MSFD aims to achieve Good Environmental Status (GES) of EU marine waters through coordinated monitoring, protection, and sustainable use. The SCORE project contributes directly to these objectives by developing innovative, ecosystem-based tools and participatory approaches that enhance the resilience of coastal cities. By combining citizen science, NbS, and digital technologies such as the ICT Platform and Digital Twin, SCORE strengthens the scientific and technical foundations for assessing and managing marine environmental pressures, particularly those linked to climate change, flooding, and coastal erosion.

(d) Gaps in MSFD Implementation⁴

The European Court of Auditors in 2020 highlighted the following gaps with regard to the MSFD and its implementation (European Court of Auditors, 2020):

- Knowledge gaps including a lack of data available on Member States's marine waters, and lack of important ecological dimensions in the indicators of good environmental status (GES) (for example, absence of consideration of microbial communities);
- Lack of sufficient measures (and lack of funding thereof) to attain good environmental status;
- Lack of engagement of economic and private stakeholders beyond public authorities;
- Lack of policy coherence (e.g. with the Common Fisheries Policy).

Other gaps include:

- The directive does not explicitly address the impacts of climate change on coastal areas, including sea-level rise, coastal erosion, and extreme weather events, though these significantly affect marine ecosystems and coastal resilience.

⁴ IEEP, ICLEI, IUCN, UNEP-WCMC, Biodiversa+ (2024). NetworkNature Nature-based Solutions policy screening and analysis of needs and gaps for 2024-2030 with 6 priority policy themes. EU HORIZON-CL6-2022-BIODIV-01, Project ID 101082213

- It primarily focuses on the marine environment and does not sufficiently integrate the challenges of urbanized coastal areas where marine and terrestrial ecosystems overlap.
- While the MSFD mentions economic and social analyses, it lacks robust guidance on integrating these considerations into marine strategies.
- The directive promotes public participation but provides limited frameworks for engaging local communities, industries, and stakeholders effectively.
- The directive emphasizes monitoring but lacks specific guidance on data systems for adaptive management in rapidly changing coastal environments.
- While the MSFD includes marine protected areas, it does not emphasize NbS as a primary strategy for climate adaptation and ecosystem restoration.

(e) How SCORE Outputs Can Address These Gaps

Urban-Coastal Interface Solutions: By focusing on smart climate resilience in coastal cities, SCORE provides tailored policy actions that bridge the gap between marine and urban policy, promoting integrated planning, green-blue infrastructure, and climate adaptation in densely populated coastal zones.

Embedding Socio-Economic Analysis: SCORE offers methodologies for embedding socio-economic considerations into marine and coastal management, including the valuation of ecosystem services, improved livelihoods, and sustainable tourism, addressing the MSFD's limited guidance in this area.

Participatory Tools for Stakeholder Engagement: Through Living Labs, co-design workshops, and citizen science activities, SCORE develops frameworks for actively involving local communities, industries, and other stakeholders, responding to the directive's weak implementation of public participation.

Advanced Monitoring and Data Systems: SCORE promotes the use of dynamic monitoring tools, such as low-cost sensors and real-time data platforms, to support adaptive management. This helps fill the directive's gap in actionable guidance on data systems in coastal environments.

Mainstreaming NbS: SCORE prioritizes EBA (such as dune restoration, wetland conservation, and green dykes) as core strategies for coastal protection and climate adaptation, complementing and enhancing the MSFD's focus on marine protected areas.

Bridging Marine and Terrestrial Governance: SCORE promotes integrated policy frameworks that link marine and land-based planning systems, encouraging cross-sectoral coordination that is essential but underdeveloped in the MSFD.

4.1.2 Water Framework Directive (WFD)

(a) Short Description of the Policy

The Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC), established in 2000, is the EU's primary legislation for the protection and management of water resources. Its main objective is to achieve 'good status' for all EU surface and groundwater bodies, including rivers, lakes, transitional waters, and coastal waters, by 2015. The directive promotes an integrated river basin management approach, requiring Member States to develop and implement River Basin Management Plans (RBMPs) that outline strategies for protecting and improving water quality within their respective river basins.

Key components of the Water Framework Directive (WFD) include the characterization of River Basin Districts, which involves assessing the physical, chemical, and ecological status of water bodies. It also entails conducting an

economic analysis of water use to evaluate the economic aspects of water utilization and support sustainable management practices. Monitoring programs are established to regularly assess the status of water bodies and track progress toward environmental objectives. Additionally, the WFD emphasizes public participation, encouraging active involvement of stakeholders and the wider public in water management decisions. The directive also emphasizes the 'polluter pays' principle, ensuring that those responsible for pollution bear the costs of necessary measures to restore water quality.

(b) Key Initiatives Supporting the Policy

Several EU initiatives complement the WFD, like the:

Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive: Aims to protect the environment from the adverse effects of urban wastewater discharges.

Nitrates Directive: Seeks to reduce water pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources.

Groundwater Directive: Focuses on preventing and controlling groundwater pollution.

Floods Directive (see next chapter): Addresses the assessment and management of flood risks to reduce adverse consequences for human health, the environment, and economic activity.

(c) Relation with the SCORE Project

The SCORE project aligns with the objectives of the WFD through several key actions. It improves water monitoring by deploying low-cost sensors and digital tools that enhance real-time tracking of water quality. The project also promotes NbS, with Living Labs showcasing how wetlands and natural water retention measures (NWRMs) can contribute to improved ecological status. Additionally, SCORE strengthens stakeholder engagement by empowering local communities through initiatives such as the Citizen Science Playbook and Community Geosurveys. Finally, it enhances risk assessments by using digital twin models and climate risk assessment tools to support informed decision-making in integrated water management.

(d) Gaps in WFD Implementation

Despite its comprehensive framework, the WFD faces key implementation gaps, including:

- Although natural water retention measures (NWRMs) are recognized, they are not systematically integrated into River Basin Management Plans (RBMPs).
- The directive does not fully address the impacts of climate change on water availability, pollution, and disaster risk reduction.
- Some Member States fail to submit or fully implement RBMPs, causing delays in meeting water quality objectives.
- Although public participation is a core principle, engagement remains low in many regions.
- NbS compete with grey infrastructure for investment, leading to a preference for traditional engineering solutions.

(e) How SCORE Outputs Can Address These Gaps

The SCORE project offers practical solutions to address these challenges:

Integrating NbS into River Basin Management: Living Labs demonstrate effective EBA measures for water quality improvement.

Enhancing Climate Adaptation in Water Management: Risk assessment tools help incorporate climate resilience into water strategies.

Improving Public Engagement: Citizen Science Playbook and community-driven monitoring increase participation in WFD implementation.

Strengthening Water Quality Monitoring: Low-cost sensors improve real-time data collection and analysis.

Providing Financial Strategies for Water Management: Decision-support tools help cities and regions secure funding for WFD-related measures

4.1.3 Flood Directive

(a) Short Description of the Policy

The EU Floods Directive (2007/60/EC) establishes a framework for the assessment and management of flood risks across European river basins and coastal areas. Its primary objective is to reduce the adverse consequences of flooding for human health, the environment, cultural heritage, and economic activity. Recognizing that floods are natural phenomena that cannot be prevented, the directive emphasizes risk reduction, prevention, preparedness, and coordinated response measures.

The directive requires Member States to conduct preliminary flood risk assessments, prepare flood hazard and risk maps, and develop flood risk management plans. These plans must take into account the impacts of climate change, ensuring long-term resilience. A core principle of the directive is cooperation across national borders, especially for shared river basins, to ensure that flood management actions in one country do not adversely impact neighbouring states.

(b) Key Initiatives Supporting the Policy

Several EU and national-level initiatives support the implementation and effectiveness of the Floods Directive:

Water Framework Directive: Ensures that flood risk management aligns with sustainable water management and promotes river basin cooperation.

EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change: Helps Member States integrate climate adaptation measures into flood risk management, recognizing the role of NbS in flood prevention.

Cohesion Fund & European Regional Development Fund (ERDF): Provide financial support for flood risk reduction projects, such as early warning systems, infrastructure improvements, and nature-based flood defenses.

EU Civil Protection Mechanism: Facilitates cross-border cooperation in disaster response and preparedness, including flood risk monitoring and emergency response coordination among Member States.

EU Solidarity Fund (EUSF): Offers rapid financial assistance to EU countries affected by major natural disasters, including severe floods.

European Green Deal & Biodiversity Strategy 2030: Promote NbS such as wetland restoration and sustainable land management to enhance flood resilience while preserving biodiversity.

Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS): Provides real-time flood monitoring and satellite-based flood hazard mapping to support emergency response and disaster risk management (see chapter 7 on ECFAS).

These initiatives collectively reinforce the Floods Directive by ensuring that flood risk assessments, early warning systems, and adaptation strategies are continuously improved and aligned with EU-wide climate resilience and disaster risk reduction efforts.

(c) Relation with the SCORE Project

The SCORE project directly aligns with flood prevention and coastal city resilience. The project aims to study, design, develop, monitor, and validate adaptation measures for coastal and low-lying areas to protect them from increasing climate and sea level risks, including coastal flooding and erosion.

Specifically, the SCORE project contributes to the implementation of the Floods Directive by advancing multi-hazard risk assessments through its Digital Twin Platform and GIS-based Early Warning System, which offer real-time monitoring and scenario-based flood projections. It integrates citizen science and participatory approaches (e.g. Community Geosurveys, low-cost sensors, and the Citizen Science Playbook) to enhance flood awareness and support data collection efforts. The project also promotes EBA that help reduce flood risks while simultaneously enhancing biodiversity and ecosystem services. Additionally, SCORE delivers decision-support tools for flood risk management, including the Risk-Based Investment Planning Tool, which assists policymakers in prioritizing adaptation investments and developing financial resilience strategies.

SCORE's data-driven, participatory, and ecosystem-based approaches directly support the directive's objectives by improving flood risk assessment, early warning systems, and climate adaptation strategies in European coastal cities.

(d) Gaps in Floods Directive Implementation

Despite its comprehensive framework, the Floods Directive faces several challenges in implementation. Key gaps include:

- The directive primarily emphasizes grey infrastructure solutions (e.g. levees, dikes), with insufficient focus on green and blue infrastructure such as wetland restoration and natural floodplains. The European Commission's review of the second cycle of Flood Risk Management Plans (2016–2021) identified this as a significant barrier.
- Flood risk management plans are not always aligned with broader climate resilience strategies, leading to fragmented adaptation efforts. The European Court of Auditors (2018) also pointed to a lack of guidance on integrating flood management with climate change mitigation.
- There is no clear framework for managing shared flooding zones, and flood risk management plans often do not include measures taken by other involved Member States. This gap is particularly problematic for the 'solidarity principle,' as upstream Member States have no incentives to implement measures benefiting downstream neighbours (Wild et al., 2020).
- Short-term political cycles hinder the implementation of sustainable, long-term flood risk reduction measures, particularly those based on ecosystem restoration. There is also a lack of dedicated funding for large-scale river restoration and measures ensuring synergies with the Floods Directive and the Habitats Directive, such as Natural Water Retention Measures.
- Although public consultation is required, participatory approaches such as citizen science are not systematically integrated into flood risk management plans. Additionally, there is a lack of awareness among stakeholders about the benefits of NbS and their integration at a landscape level.

(e) How SCORE Outputs Can Address These Gaps

The SCORE project provides several innovative solutions that directly address the gaps in the Floods Directive's implementation:

Enhancing NbS Integration: The EBA catalogue developed in SCORE provides evidence-based NbS strategies (e.g. wetland restoration, urban green spaces, sustainable drainage systems) that can be incorporated into flood risk management plans.

Bridging Policy and Climate Adaptation Efforts: SCORE's multi-hazard risk assessment methodologies ensure that flood risk management is fully aligned with climate change adaptation strategies, creating a cohesive policy framework.

Improving Long-Term Planning and Investment Strategies: SCORE's Risk-Based Investment Planning Tool and Financial Resilience Strategies offer structured decision-support mechanisms for sustainable financing and long-term flood mitigation planning.

Advancing Stakeholder Engagement and Citizen Science: SCORE's Community Geosurveys, Low-Cost Sensors, and Citizen Science Playbook empower local communities to contribute flood-related data and participate in decision-making, improving the transparency and inclusivity of flood risk planning.

Deploying Digital and AI-Powered Early Warning Systems: SCORE's GIS-Based Early Warning System and Digital Twin Platform provide real-time flood monitoring, predictive analytics, and scenario simulations, enhancing flood preparedness and response.

4.1.4 EU Nature Directives (Birds, Habitats, Natura sites)

(a) Short Description of the Policy

The Birds Directive (Directive 2009/147/EC) and the Habitats Directive (Directive 92/43/EEC) are referred to as the EU Nature Directives and form the cornerstones of the EU's biodiversity conservation policy. Together, they form the legal framework for nature conservation in Europe by establishing the Natura 2000 network, the largest coordinated network of protected areas in the world.

The Birds Directive aims to protect all wild bird species naturally occurring in the EU by setting conservation measures, regulating hunting and exploitation, and designating Special Protection Areas (SPAs) to safeguard essential habitats.

The Habitats Directive focuses on protecting natural habitats and species of European importance by requiring Member States to designate Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) and implement conservation measures. It introduces the ecosystem-based approach to conservation, ensuring sustainable land use and biodiversity restoration across ecosystems such as forests, wetlands, and coastal areas.

These two directives collectively preserve Europe's biodiversity, maintain ecological balance, and support sustainable development through long-term habitat protection and species conservation.

(b) Key Initiatives Supporting the Policy

Several key EU initiatives support the implementation of the Birds and Habitats Directives:

Natura 2000 Network: The largest network of protected areas globally, covering 18% of EU land and 8% of its marine environment. Ensures the long-term conservation of habitats and species while allowing sustainable human activities.

EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030: Expands protected areas and aims to restore degraded ecosystems across Europe. Focuses on strict protection of old-growth forests, wetlands, and marine ecosystems.

LIFE Programme: EU's primary funding instrument for environmental and climate action projects. Supports the conservation of species, restoration of habitats, and implementation of Natura 2000 management plans.

Green Infrastructure Strategy: Promotes NbS to enhance ecosystem resilience, reduce fragmentation, and improve habitat connectivity.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD): Ensures marine biodiversity conservation and aligns with the Habitats Directive in protecting marine species and ecosystems.

Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) & Agri-Environmental Measures: Encourages biodiversity-friendly farming practices to protect species and habitats in rural landscapes.

These initiatives collectively reinforce the legal and financial mechanisms needed to implement the Birds and Habitats Directives, ensuring biodiversity protection and ecosystem resilience in the EU.

(c) Relation with the SCORE Project

The Birds and Habitats Directives, which form the legal basis for the Natura 2000 network, aim to protect biodiversity and ensure the long-term conservation of Europe's most vulnerable species and habitats. The SCORE project aligns with these directives through its focus on EBA and NbS in CCLs. These strategies not only enhance climate resilience but also contribute to biodiversity conservation by restoring and managing coastal ecosystems such as wetlands, dunes, and marine habitats, many of which are part of Natura 2000 sites.

By integrating NbS, the SCORE project actively supports the objectives of the Habitats and Birds Directives by promoting sustainable land and water management in coastal areas, reducing the impacts of climate change on protected habitats, and ensuring the coexistence of human activities with ecological conservation. Additionally, SCORE's participatory approaches, including citizen science and digital tools, foster better public engagement and local stewardship of protected areas, aligning with the Directives' goal of involving stakeholders in conservation efforts.

(d) Gaps in Natura and Habitats Directives Implementation

Despite their critical role in biodiversity conservation, the implementation of the Birds and Habitats Directives faces several challenges. Key gaps include:

- The directives are not consistently embedded into sectoral policies such as climate adaptation, urban planning, and disaster risk reduction. This lack of harmonization limits the potential for synergies between biodiversity conservation and climate resilience.
- Major funding shortages hinder the achievement of the directives' objectives. There are barriers to accessing available EU funding, as well as gaps in evidence regarding the effectiveness and efficiency of funding in fulfilling conservation goals (European Commission DG ENV, 2022).
- While the directives set clear conservation objectives, implementation varies across EU Member States. Some Natura 2000 sites face habitat degradation due to urban expansion, unsustainable tourism, and climate change impacts. The lack of robust monitoring and enforcement mechanisms exacerbates these challenges.

- Delays in adopting long-term conservation strategies are often driven by shifting political priorities and bureaucratic complexities. These factors undermine the consistent application of conservation measures.
- Local communities and businesses often lack awareness or incentives to actively participate in conservation efforts. This reduces opportunities for co-benefits between biodiversity protection and climate adaptation, further weakening the directives' impact.

(e) How SCORE Outputs Can Address These Gaps

The SCORE project offers concrete solutions to address these implementation gaps by leveraging science-based, participatory, and digital approaches to integrate biodiversity conservation with climate adaptation in coastal cities.

EBA Solutions: By restoring and enhancing coastal habitats such as dunes, wetlands, and seagrass meadows, SCORE's EBA strategies directly contribute to the objectives of the Birds and Habitats Directives. These actions support species protection and ecosystem resilience, helping Natura 2000 sites withstand climate change pressures.

GIS-Based Monitoring and Digital Twin Platform: SCORE's ICT tools, including the GIS-based monitoring system and Digital Twin Platform, enable better mapping, monitoring, and prediction of biodiversity changes in protected areas. These tools enhance decision-making processes by providing real-time data on ecosystem health and climate risks.

Citizen Science and Stakeholder Engagement: SCORE fosters participatory conservation through initiatives like the Citizen Science Playbook and Community Geosurveys, increasing public involvement in monitoring and protecting Natura 2000 sites. By engaging local authorities, businesses, and communities, SCORE promotes a more inclusive and sustainable governance model.

Financial Strategies for NbS: Through its investment and financial resilience tools, SCORE provides guidance on funding mechanisms that support long-term conservation financing, helping bridge the financial gap in Natura 2000 management.

4.1.5 Biodiversity Strategy

(a) Short Description of the Strategy

The EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 is a comprehensive policy framework aimed at halting biodiversity loss and restoring ecosystems across Europe. It is a key component of the European Green Deal and aligns with global commitments under the UN Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). The strategy aims to protect at least 30% of the EU's land and marine areas and restore degraded ecosystems by 2030. It introduces legally binding nature restoration targets, emphasizes the importance of green infrastructure and NbS, and integrates biodiversity considerations into economic sectors such as agriculture, fisheries, and forestry.

The strategy also highlights the need for stronger enforcement of existing EU nature laws, such as the Birds and Habitats Directives, and promotes increased funding for biodiversity conservation. It sets ambitious targets, including planting three billion trees, reducing pesticide use by 50%, and restoring at least 25,000 km of free-flowing rivers across the EU.

(b) Key Initiatives Supporting the Strategy

Several initiatives and legislative proposals support the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, ensuring the implementation of its goals:

Nature Restoration Law: Aims to set legally binding targets for restoring degraded ecosystems, focusing on wetlands, forests, and marine environments.

EU Nature Protection Targets: Expands protected areas to cover at least 30% of land and sea, with 10% under strict protection for ecosystems with high biodiversity value.

Pollinator Initiative: Strengthens efforts to reverse the decline of pollinators, which are critical for biodiversity and food security.

EU Forest Strategy for 2030: Focuses on forest conservation, afforestation, and climate resilience, ensuring that forests continue to provide ecological and economic benefits.

EU Green Infrastructure: Promotes NbS to address climate adaptation, including the restoration of urban green spaces, floodplains, and wetlands.

Sustainable Finance and Biodiversity Funding: Expands EU funding mechanisms, including the LIFE Programme, Horizon Europe, and the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), to support biodiversity conservation and ecosystem restoration.

(c) Relation with the SCORE Project

SCORE project aligns with the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 by integrating NbS to enhance climate resilience in coastal cities. By implementing NbS, SCORE contributes to restoring degraded ecosystems, a key objective of the EU strategy. Additionally, SCORE's co-creation approach, involving citizens and stakeholders through CCLLs, promotes community engagement in biodiversity conservation efforts.

(d) Gaps in EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 Implementation

The European Union's Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 is an ambitious plan aimed at halting biodiversity loss and promoting ecosystem restoration. However, several gaps and challenges have been identified in its implementation:

- Effective implementation requires robust coordination both among and within EU Member States. Past conservation efforts have suffered from fragmented actions due to inadequate coordination, leading to inconsistent policy applications and monitoring protocols.
- Biodiversity considerations are often not sufficiently integrated into sectors such as agriculture, fisheries, and urban planning. This lack of integration can result in policies that conflict with conservation objectives, undermining biodiversity goals.
- There is a significant funding gap in biodiversity conservation efforts. Insufficient financial resources hinder the effective implementation and enforcement of conservation measures, jeopardizing the achievement of the strategy's objectives.
- Limited stakeholder engagement in decision-making processes can reduce the effectiveness of conservation policies and lead to conflicts. Enhancing governance through inclusive participation is crucial for the success of biodiversity initiatives.
- Despite the designation of marine protected areas (MPAs), over 80% have been found to be ineffective in meeting conservation goals due to minimal protection from industrial activities. This indicates a gap between policy intentions and on-ground effectiveness.
- Establishing a unified framework for monitoring and reporting biodiversity data across Member States is essential. Current disparities in data collection and reporting hinder the assessment of progress and the identification of areas needing improvement.

Addressing these gaps is crucial for the EU to achieve its biodiversity objectives by 2030.

(e) How SCORE Outputs Can Address These Gaps

SCORE addresses several gaps and challenges identified in the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 through its specific objectives:

Ecosystem Restoration: By implementing NbS, SCORE contributes to restoring degraded coastal ecosystems, enhancing biodiversity and ecosystem services.

Knowledge Integration: SCORE consolidates knowledge on the effectiveness of NbS in mitigating climate-related risks, supporting evidence-based policy-making for biodiversity conservation.

Social Acceptance: Through active stakeholder engagement in CCLs, SCORE enhances social acceptance of NbS, facilitating their broader adoption in coastal management.

Policy Support: SCORE's findings and methodologies can inform policy frameworks, supporting the implementation of the EU Biodiversity Strategy's objectives at local and national levels.

4.1.6 EU Climate Change Adaptation Strategy

(a) Short Description of the Strategy

The EU Climate Adaptation Strategy, officially titled "*Forging a Climate-Resilient Europe - the new EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change*," was adopted by the European Commission in February 2021. It builds on the 2013 Adaptation Strategy and aligns with the European Green Deal, aiming to create a climate-resilient society by 2050. Recognizing that climate change impacts, such as extreme weather events, biodiversity loss, and rising sea levels, are unavoidable even with successful emission reductions, the strategy focuses on enhancing preparedness, resilience, and adaptive capacity at all levels of governance.

The strategy emphasizes "smarter, swifter, and more systemic" adaptation by focusing on several key priorities. It aims to improve knowledge and data through enhanced climate risk assessments, targeted research, and the development of open-access information platforms. Adaptation is integrated across all sectors and policies, ensuring that economic activities, urban planning, agriculture, and infrastructure are designed to be climate-resilient. The strategy also seeks to accelerate adaptation actions by promoting nature-based solutions, increasing investment, and reinforcing risk management mechanisms. Furthermore, it underscores the importance of enhancing global leadership by supporting international efforts to build climate resilience, with a particular focus on vulnerable regions.

With economic losses from climate-related disasters already averaging €12 billion per year⁵ in the EU, the strategy underscores the urgent need to reduce vulnerabilities, mainstream adaptation into policies, and increase financial investments in resilience-building initiatives.

(b) Key Initiatives Supporting the Strategy

The EU Climate Adaptation Strategy is supported by multiple initiatives and programs that facilitate adaptation efforts across different sectors. Some of the key initiatives include:

Climate-ADAPT Platform: The Climate-ADAPT portal serves as the primary knowledge hub for climate adaptation in Europe. It provides data, tools, case studies, and best practices to inform decision-making at local, national, and EU levels.

⁵ European Commission (2021). *Closing the climate protection gap – Commission Staff Working Document*. Directorate-General for Climate Action.

Horizon Europe Research & Innovation Programs: The Adaptation to Climate Change Mission under Horizon Europe focuses on researching and piloting innovative adaptation solutions, such as early warning systems, resilient infrastructure, and digital climate services.

NbS for Adaptation: Recognizing the role of ecosystems in climate resilience, the EU promotes green infrastructure, wetlands restoration, afforestation, and coastal protection projects. These measures provide dual benefits for biodiversity conservation and climate adaptation.

Integration into Macroeconomic Policies & Investments: The EU mainstreams climate resilience into budgetary and financial mechanisms, such as the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF), Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Finance, which directs investments into climate-resilient sectors.

Stronger Risk Management & Disaster Preparedness: The strategy prioritizes improving climate risk assessments and the Union Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM) to better prepare for climate-related disasters such as floods, droughts, and wildfires.

Promoting Local & Regional Adaptation: The EU supports local adaptation plans through several initiatives. The EU Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy assists cities in creating and implementing climate adaptation strategies. Rural areas and regions also benefit from targeted funding programs that address their specific adaptation needs. Additionally, the EU places strong emphasis on fostering climate resilience in vulnerable communities, ensuring that adaptation efforts are inclusive and equitable across all territories.

International Climate Resilience & Adaptation Finance: The EU scales up climate finance for developing countries through the Green Climate Fund (GCF), Adaptation Fund (AF) and Partnerships with African and Small Island Developing States (SIDS) to build resilience.

These initiatives collectively advance the EU's goal of a climate-resilient society, ensuring that adaptation efforts are well-funded, widely implemented, and scientifically informed.

(c) Relation with the SCORE Project

The EU Climate Adaptation Strategy aims to enhance climate resilience across Europe, particularly in vulnerable areas such as coastal regions. It promotes a systemic, knowledge-driven, and action-oriented approach, focusing on NbS, digital innovation, and community engagement. The SCORE project aligns closely with these objectives by integrating EBAs, digital tools, and community-driven climate adaptation solutions in coastal cities.

SCORE's CCLLs serve as pilot sites for performing socioeconomic assessments of EBA solutions targeting their main climate hazards, testing and implementing NbS and deploying low-cost sensors viable for citizen science activities, directly supporting the EU strategy's goal of smarter, more systemic, and swifter adaptation. Furthermore, by incorporating early-warning systems, digital twin monitoring, and citizen engagement, SCORE helps address climate uncertainty and disaster preparedness in line with the EU strategy's emphasis on data-driven and inclusive adaptation measures.

(d) Gaps in EU Climate Change Adaptation Strategy Implementation⁶

Despite the ambitious goals of the EU Climate Adaptation Strategy, its implementation faces significant gaps and challenges, particularly in terms of reporting effectiveness, local awareness, funding allocation, and risk of maladaptation, notably:

- One key gap is the ineffectiveness of reporting mechanisms. While the EU adaptation framework is comprehensive, Member States often rely on outdated scientific data for their National Adaptation Strategies (NAS) and plans. Moreover, reporting on adaptation efforts remains inconsistent, with insufficient data quality and lack of common indicators, making it difficult to track progress effectively. Many national reports offer only qualitative descriptions rather than quantitative assessments of progress. As a result, the European Commission and Member States lack a clear picture of adaptation advancements and challenges, which hinders informed decision-making.
- Another major challenge is the low local awareness and usage of EU adaptation tools. A survey⁷ of 400 municipalities found that nearly 70% were unaware of the EU Climate Adaptation Strategy, and over 60% had no knowledge of their national adaptation plans. This lack of awareness limits the uptake of EU-funded adaptation resources, such as Climate-ADAPT, Copernicus, and the EU Covenant of Mayors, reducing their potential impact at the local level. Given that local communities are crucial actors in adaptation efforts, this gap weakens bottom-up resilience-building initiatives and hampers local preparedness for climate risks.
- Additionally, EU adaptation funding favours short-term over long-term solutions, leading to a risk of maladaptation. While over €26 billion⁸ has been allocated for adaptation in the 2021-2027 period, a significant portion of funded projects fail to enhance adaptive capacity in the long run. For instance, some projects promote irrigation expansion rather than transitioning to less water-intensive crops, or invest in artificial snow cannons instead of diversifying tourism economies. Such projects create dependency on unsustainable practices, rather than fostering true climate resilience. The lack of funding mechanisms that prioritize long-term, nature-based, and systemic adaptation further exacerbates these risks.
- Lastly, the fragmentation of adaptation governance and conflicting sectoral priorities limit the strategy's effectiveness. Some national frameworks simultaneously promote water conservation and increased irrigation, leading to conflicting adaptation goals. Similarly, while the EU has strengthened its policy focus on NbS, such measures remain underutilized compared to traditional, infrastructure-heavy approaches like dykes and seawalls. This imbalance highlights the need for stronger integration of NbS into adaptation policies, as well as more cross-sectoral coordination.

Addressing these gaps requires improved reporting mechanisms, greater local engagement, a shift toward long-term resilience investments, and better integration of NbS into adaptation planning. Without these improvements, the EU's ambition to become a climate-resilient society by 2050 may fall short of its goals.

(e) How SCORE Outputs Can Address These Gaps

The SCORE project provides practical solutions to many of the gaps in the implementation of the EU Climate Adaptation Strategy, particularly in reporting mechanisms, local engagement, long-term resilience investments, and governance coherence. By integrating NbS, digital innovation, and participatory planning, SCORE directly

⁶ **European Court of Auditors (2024).** *Special Report 15/2024: Climate adaptation in the EU – Action not keeping up with ambition.* Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Available at: <https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/publications/SR-2024-15>

⁷ **European Court of Auditors (2024).** *EU risks falling behind in the race for climate adaptation.* Special Report 15/2024. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/publications/SR-2024-15>

⁸ **European Court of Auditors (2024).** *Climate adaptation in the EU – Challenges in implementation and funding.* Special Report 15/2024. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Available at: <https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/publications/SR-2024-15>

supports the EU's goal of building a climate-resilient society by 2050. Examples of how SCORE can address the previous gaps are described below:

Strengthening Reporting Mechanisms and Data Quality: One of the critical gaps in the EU Adaptation Strategy is the lack of effective reporting mechanisms and standardized indicators. SCORE addresses this by implementing Digital Twin solutions, which enable real-time monitoring of climate risks and adaptation progress in coastal cities. These tools help local and national authorities improve data accuracy, comparability, and long-term tracking of adaptation measures. By providing clear, measurable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for adaptation actions, SCORE ensures better alignment between local and EU-wide climate resilience objectives.

Enhancing Local Awareness and Participation: The low awareness and uptake of EU adaptation tools at the local level remains a significant challenge. SCORE directly tackles this issue through CCLs, which serve as platforms for community engagement, stakeholder collaboration, and hands-on adaptation initiatives. By involving citizens, local businesses, and policymakers in the co-design of EBA, SCORE fosters bottom-up climate action, ensuring that adaptation strategies are not only technically sound but also socially accepted and sustainable. Additionally, Citizen Science Kits allow residents to actively monitor local climate risks, strengthening community resilience and engagement.

Shifting Investment Priorities Toward Long-Term Adaptation: EU adaptation funding has been criticized for favouring short-term over long-term resilience solutions, leading to risks of maladaptation. SCORE provides financial resilience strategies that guide cities toward sustainable, long-term adaptation investments. Instead of short-term infrastructural fixes like seawalls, SCORE promotes NbS (e.g. wetland restoration and green buffers) that offer long-lasting climate resilience. The project also develops investment models and conducts socioeconomic assessments of EBA solutions using multicriteria analysis (MCA) and cost-benefit analysis (CBA), supporting policymakers in justifying and securing long-term funding for sustainable adaptation projects.

Reducing the Risk of Maladaptation: Many adaptation projects in the EU reinforce existing vulnerabilities rather than reducing them (e.g. expanding irrigation instead of promoting water-efficient crops). SCORE mitigates this risk by providing decision-support tools that help policymakers evaluate the long-term consequences of adaptation choices. By emphasizing EBA and integrated coastal zone management (ICZM), SCORE ensures that adaptation efforts do not exacerbate climate risks but instead enhance overall resilience.

Scaling Up Cross-Border Cooperation and Knowledge Sharing: A key weakness in EU adaptation efforts is the limited coordination between cities and regions. SCORE bridges this gap by facilitating transnational knowledge exchange through its network of CCLs. These hubs connect coastal cities across Europe, allowing them to share best practices, data, and successful adaptation models. Additionally, SCORE's digital knowledge platform provides an open-access repository of tested and validated adaptation strategies, ensuring that lessons learned in one region can be replicated in others. SCORE has also created clusters (ex Adapt4Coast⁹) and collaborations with other EU projects to enhance climate resilience in European coastal areas.

Harnessing Technological Innovations for Climate Resilience: The EU's adaptation strategy calls for smarter, data-driven solutions, yet many local governments lack the technological capacity to implement them. SCORE fills this gap by developing advanced digital tools such as smart sensing systems, AI-driven climate risk models, and real-time monitoring platforms. These technologies empower cities to anticipate climate impacts, simulate adaptation scenarios, and take proactive measures before disasters occur.

⁹ <https://score-eu-project.eu/2023/11/29/adapt4coast-4-eu-projects-join-forces-to-enhance-climate-change-adaptation/>

By addressing these critical gaps in implementation, the SCORE project enhances the EU's capacity to adapt to climate change in a more systemic, inclusive, and forward-thinking way.

4.2. International Policy

4.2.1 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

(a) Short Description of the SDGs

The 17 SDGs form the backbone of the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015. They represent a global call to action to end poverty, protect the planet, and ensure peace and prosperity for all by 2030. The SDGs cover a broad spectrum of challenges, including health, education, inequality, economic growth, climate change, biodiversity loss, and sustainable urban development.

These goals are deeply interconnected, i.e. progress in one area often contributes to others, making an integrated and balanced policy approach essential. The SDGs promote action not only by governments but also by civil society, businesses, and individuals. By navigating synergies and trade-offs between goals, stakeholders can work together more effectively to address complex global issues like climate resilience, ocean protection, and social equity.

(b) Key Initiatives Supporting the SDGs

SDGs are supported by a wide range of initiatives, funding programmes, and partnerships designed to help countries implement the 2030 Agenda.

At the Global Level:

UN SDG Fund: Provides catalytic funding for innovative development projects aligned with the SDGs.

High-Level Political Forum on Sustainable Development (HLPF): Oversees global progress, encourages voluntary national reviews (VNRs), and fosters peer learning.

Global Partnership for Sustainable Development Data: Supports countries in using data to monitor SDG progress.

United Nations Development Programme (UNDP): Plays a lead role in supporting countries in integrating the SDGs into national development plans.

At the EU Level:

European Green Deal: Aligns directly with many SDGs, especially those related to climate, biodiversity, and sustainable cities.

NextGenerationEU & Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF): Provides funding for SDG-aligned recovery and transition, including green and digital transformation.

European Semester: Integrates SDG progress into economic and social policy coordination.

Horizon Europe: Supports SDG-aligned research and innovation, particularly through Missions and Clusters (e.g. climate, oceans, cities).

EU Taxonomy & Sustainable Finance Strategy: Channels public and private investments toward SDG-compliant activities.

(c) Relation with the SCORE Project

The following SDGs are directly related to SCORE project:

“SDG 13 Climate Action” urges countries to take urgent and meaningful steps to combat climate change and its impacts through mitigation, adaptation, resilience-building, and education. It calls for integrating climate measures into national policies, strengthening early warning systems, and supporting vulnerable communities in adapting to climate-related hazards.

The SCORE project directly supports Goal 13 by developing innovative tools such as digital twins, GIS-based early warning systems, and EBA strategies that help coastal cities become more resilient to flooding, erosion, and sea-level rise. SCORE’s work in participatory planning, citizen science, and real-time data collection empowers local communities and decision-makers to prepare for and respond to climate threats effectively.

SCORE contributes to “Goal 11 Sustainable Cities and Communities” by creating more inclusive, safe, and resilient urban areas by supporting smart adaptation solutions tailored to coastal cities.

Through its nature-based solutions and support for integrated coastal zone management (ICZM), SCORE helps protect marine ecosystems and coastal biodiversity and thus also contributes to “Goal 14: Life Below Water”.

The SCORE consortium brings together researchers, cities, and citizens across Europe, fostering international collaboration and knowledge-sharing for sustainable development, contributing to “Goal 17: Partnerships for the Goals”

(d) Gaps in SDGs Implementation¹⁰

Despite the global ambition embedded in the SDGs, including SDG 13 on Climate Action, significant implementation gaps persist.

- One of the most pressing challenges is the lack of mechanisms to support local-level action. Although national strategies exist, the SDG framework provides insufficient guidance and resources for municipalities and regional authorities (i.e. those most affected by climate impacts) to translate commitments into tangible outcomes. Many local governments lack the technical capacity, financial resources, or policy autonomy to implement effective adaptation and mitigation measures (The Climate News, 2024).
- Moreover, while the SDGs are designed to be interlinked, their implementation is often siloed and fragmented, with little effort to navigate trade-offs or synergies between goals. For example, the pursuit of “SDG 8 Decent work and economic growth” or “SDG 9 Industry, Innovation and infrastructure” can conflict with climate objectives if not approached through sustainable pathways. As Häyhä et al. (2020)¹¹ highlight, this disconnect can reinforce unsustainable development models rather than encourage systems change. SDG 13, in particular, is vulnerable to this issue, as short-term economic priorities frequently override long-term climate resilience planning.
- Another critical weakness is the limited monitoring, evaluation, and accountability associated with SDG implementation. The framework suffers from ambiguous indicators, inconsistent baseline data, and voluntary reporting mechanisms, making it difficult to track genuine progress, especially at the subnational level where most climate risks materialize. This gap is especially acute for SDG 13, where accurate, real-time, and localized data is essential but often unavailable or unused in decision-making (The Climate News, 2024).

¹⁰ The Climate News (2023). *The Pros and Cons of the SDG Framework*. Available at: <https://theclimatenews.co.uk/the-pros-and-cons-of-the-sdg-framework> [Accessed 10 Apr. 2025].

¹¹ Sjøfjell, Beate and Häyhä, Tiina and Cornell, Sarah, A Research-Based Approach to the UN Sustainable Development Goals. A Prerequisite to Sustainable Business (January 28, 2020). University of Oslo Faculty of Law Research Paper No. 2020-02, Nordic & European Company Law Working Paper No. 21-12, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3526744> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3526744>

- In terms of solutions, the SDGs still underemphasize NbS, despite their growing recognition as cost-effective and ecologically sound options for climate adaptation. There is limited operational guidance or policy support within SDG 13 to prioritize NbS over traditional grey infrastructure, particularly in coastal and urban areas where ecosystems provide critical buffers against climate hazards.
- Lastly, there is a gap in stakeholder engagement and political accountability. Although the SDGs promote participation, they do not provide effective mechanisms for including marginalized voices, civil society, or youth in policy processes. The voluntary nature of national SDG commitments further weakens enforcement and limits the political will required for more ambitious and equitable climate action.

(e) How SCORE Outputs Can Address These Gaps

Insufficient local-level action: The SCORE project tackles the challenge of insufficient local-level action by empowering coastal cities through a suite of tools and platforms. With outputs like hazard maps, coastal erosion models, flood risk assessments, and the GIS-based Early Warning System, SCORE strengthens the capacity of municipalities to assess their local climate risks and plan accordingly. Tools such as the Digital Twin Platform and ICT Platform enable integrated, localized simulation and monitoring, making real-time, climate-sensitive planning more accessible to urban authorities. In addition, SCORE promotes community engagement and knowledge-building by incorporating low-cost sensors viable for citizen science activities, and by supporting actions involving local and regional stakeholders, including education, dissemination activities, and participatory-based assessments. These initiatives help improve awareness, foster inclusivity, and encourage active participation from citizens and other groups in local adaptation efforts.

Fragmentation of SDG implementation: To counteract the fragmentation of SDG implementation, SCORE promotes cross-sectoral integration. Its platforms merge data from environmental, infrastructure, and socio-economic systems, enabling policymakers to explore the interlinkages between different domains, such as flood risk, land use, and socio-economic vulnerability, thereby fostering a systemic perspective on climate resilience. For example, the Scenario-Based Cash Flow Tool help align adaptation financing with both climate and development goals.

Weak monitoring and accountability systems: In response to the weak monitoring and accountability systems of the SDG framework, SCORE introduces a variety of tools for adaptive monitoring, such as low-cost sensors, the Community Geosurveys, and a Citizen Science Framework. These tools not only improve the resolution and timeliness of environmental data but also ensure data ownership and transparency through community engagement.

Adoption of EBA strategies: On the often-neglected front of NbS, SCORE stands out by embedding EBA strategies throughout its outputs. Its EBA catalogue, socio-economic assessment tools (CBA and MCA), and real-world EBA implementations in CCLLs promote the mainstreaming of green infrastructure such as wetland restoration and dune reinforcement, supporting climate adaptation while enhancing biodiversity.

Stakeholder engagement: The project's strong focus on inclusive stakeholder engagement, including participatory-based assessment of EBA solutions using MCA method, youth-focused tools like the EBACraft (a custom game in Minecraft) workshops, and outreach tools like MOOCs, webinars, and the Citizen Science Playbook, directly supports the participatory ideals of the SDGs. By creating platforms for dialogue, co-creation, and knowledge exchange, SCORE gives voice to those traditionally left out of climate planning, helping close the gap in equity and accountability.

4.2.2 Paris Agreement

(a) Short Description of the Agreement

The Paris Agreement, adopted in December 2015 under the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), is a landmark international treaty aimed at limiting global warming to well below 2°C, with efforts to restrict the increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels. It establishes a universal, legally binding framework for climate action involving all countries, with differentiated responsibilities and capacities.

The Agreement emphasizes the need for climate resilience, adaptation, and financial and technological support for developing countries. Parties must submit Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and regularly report on their progress through a transparent monitoring system. The Paris Agreement also promotes the integration of climate considerations into broader sustainable development strategies and sets the foundation for a just transition toward low-carbon, climate-resilient economies.

(b) Key Initiatives Supporting the Agreement

The Paris Agreement is supported by a broad framework of global, regional, and EU-level initiatives that help ensure its implementation, monitoring, and continuous enhancement.

Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs): At the heart of the agreement is the system of NDCs, which are submitted by each country to outline their climate action plans for reducing emissions and adapting to climate impacts. These are reinforced through the Enhanced Transparency Framework (ETF), which ensures countries regularly report on their progress, and the Global Stocktake, conducted every five years to assess collective progress toward limiting global warming to well below 2°C and pursuing efforts to stay within 1.5°C.

Climate Finance: Climate finance plays a crucial role in supporting the goals of the Paris Agreement. Key instruments include the Green Climate Fund (GCF), the Adaptation Fund (AF) and the Global Environment Facility (GEF).

Technology mechanism: In parallel to climate finance, the Technology Mechanism facilitates the transfer and deployment of climate technologies to countries in need.

Capacity Building: The Paris Committee on Capacity-Building (PCCB) supports national institutions in enhancing their technical capabilities for climate action.

EU structures: Within the European Union, the European Green Deal and the legally binding European Climate Law provide the policy backbone for implementing the Paris Agreement. The EU has committed to becoming climate neutral by 2050 and reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030, supported through legislative tools like the Fit for 55 Package. The EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) is a cornerstone market-based mechanism that ensures emissions reductions in key sectors. Additionally, Horizon Europe's Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change funds research, innovation, and capacity-building projects to improve resilience in vulnerable regions, directly aligned with the Paris Agreement's adaptation priorities.

(c) Relation with the SCORE Project

SCORE project aligns closely with the goals of the Paris Agreement, particularly those outlined in Article 7, which calls for enhancing adaptive capacity, strengthening resilience, and reducing vulnerability to climate change¹². The project operationalizes local adaptation by equipping coastal cities with tools such as Digital Twin platforms, early warning systems, and EBA strategies, enabling municipalities to assess and respond to climate hazards like sea-level rise, coastal erosion, and extreme weather events. These tools directly support local implementation of Nationally

¹² UNFCCC (2015). *Paris Agreement*. Available at: <https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement>

Determined Contributions (NDCs) and contribute to achieving the long-term temperature and resilience targets set under the Paris framework.

SCORE also supports the Paris Agreement's emphasis on transparency, stakeholder inclusion, and capacity-building through its Living Labs, citizen science initiatives, and open-access platforms. These participatory and community-driven approaches are fully consistent with the Agreement's goals of inclusive climate governance and multilevel action.¹³

(d) Gaps in Paris Agreement Implementation

Despite its global consensus and legal force, the Paris Agreement faces several significant implementation challenges.

- A key issue is the disconnect between national climate commitments and local implementation, where cities and coastal communities often lack the resources and technical capacity to operationalize climate adaptation measures¹⁴.
- While adaptation is a core pillar of the Agreement, it remains underfunded and under-monitored, with most attention still focused on mitigation. This is particularly critical in urban coastal areas, where adaptation needs are growing rapidly due to increased exposure to flooding and sea-level rise¹⁵.
- Further gaps include the limited availability of localized, real-time climate data, and the absence of clear metrics to track adaptation progress at the subnational level¹⁶.
- In addition, although the Agreement promotes public participation and inclusivity, countries often lack structured approaches or tools to engage communities, especially those most vulnerable to climate impacts. The result is a fragmented adaptation landscape with uneven progress and limited accountability.
- Notably, while NbS are recognized in international frameworks, the Paris Agreement does not systematically integrate them as a key adaptation strategy. According to a recent report of the NetworkNature project¹⁷, NbS are “largely underexplored and underused in climate policy despite their high potential.” Furthermore, challenges in mainstreaming, governance, financing, and evidence of effectiveness continue to hinder their uptake in national climate strategies. This limits the potential for cost-effective, co-beneficial approaches to building resilience across diverse ecosystems and communities.

(e) How SCORE Outputs Can Address These Gaps

SCORE offers a suite of integrated solutions that directly respond to the gaps identified in Paris Agreement implementation.

SCORE Tools: The development of high-resolution hazard maps, scenario-based investment planning tools, and Digital Twin platforms empowers local governments to conduct robust climate risk assessments and plan long-term adaptation measures grounded in evidence. These tools not only enhance local capacity but also enable more

¹³ SCORE (2023). *Ecosystem-Based Adaptation Catalogue*. Available via: <https://score-eu-project.eu> or project deliverables section.

¹⁴ UNFCCC (2023). *Synthesis Report on the Technical Dialogue of the First Global Stocktake*. Available at: <https://unfccc.int/documents/631600>

¹⁵ Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). (2022). *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability*. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report. Cambridge University Press. Available at: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/>

¹⁶ UNFCCC (2023). *Synthesis Report on the Technical Dialogue of the First Global Stocktake*. Available at: <https://unfccc.int/documents/631600>

¹⁷ IEEP, ICLEI, IUCN, UNEP-WCMC, Biodiversa+ (2024). NetworkNature Nature-based Solutions policy screening and analysis of needs and gaps for 2024- 2030 with 6 priority policy themes. EU HORIZON-CL6-2022-BIODIV-01, Project ID 101082213

transparent, data-driven climate governance that supports national reporting under the Enhanced Transparency Framework (ETF).

Community engagement: The project's focus on community involvement, via Coastal City Living Labs, citizen science playbooks, and interactive education (e.g. EBACraft workshops and MOOCs), addresses the participatory deficit in many national frameworks. By embedding citizens in the design, implementation, and monitoring of adaptation actions, SCORE reinforces the Paris Agreement's principles of inclusive and just climate action.

EBA strategies: Furthermore, SCORE's emphasis on NbS, such as wetland restoration and sustainable drainage systems, among other solutions, helps mainstream low-carbon, EBA strategies that are still underutilized globally. Through its tools and methodologies, SCORE serves as a model for translating global climate commitments into scalable, place-based interventions.

5. POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Introduction

The SCORE policy recommendations are grounded in the knowledge generated and the challenges addressed by the project partners over four years of collaborative work aimed at enhancing climate resilience in European coastal cities. Table 2 presents the key results, outputs, and tools of the SCORE project, organised into seven major categories.

	Categories of SCORE tools	SCORE outputs and tools
1	Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Socio-economic assessment of EBA (cost-benefit analysis and multi-criteria analysis) • EBA Catalogue
2	Coastal Cities Living Labs (CCLLs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CCLL Framework • Co-Creation Toolkit • Monitoring and Evaluation
3	Participatory and Citizen Science Approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community Geosurveys platform • Low-Cost Sensors Catalogue • Citizen Science Playbook • Geodesign game • Citizen science framework
4	Financial Resilience and Risk Management Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methodology for assessing climate risk for European coastal cities • Quantitative Risk assessment (exposure database, vulnerability curves, risk profiles, replacement costs) • Financial resilience strategies and decision support tool to address residual risks
5	Data collection, downscaling and modelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of hazard flooding maps • Long-term coastal erosion analysis
6	IT solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCORE ICT platform (data hub, sensor service, Knowledge Marketplace Platform) • Digital Twin platform (User Scenario Evaluation Module, Early-Warning Support Module)
7	Educational, communicational and Capacity-Building Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Massive Open Online Courses • Other communication tools (EBA training schools, webinars, EBACraft workshops)

Table 2: SCORE outputs and tools

The following core section of this deliverable is structured around these categories. For each one, a brief description of the developed output and/or tool is provided, followed by a set of actionable recommendations targeted at

different governance levels, as presented in Table 3, and directly informed and justified by the experience and outcomes of the SCORE project.

Governance level	Context within the Policy Brief
Local level	Practical guidelines for integrating SCORE findings into local coastal management and climate adaptation strategies.
National level	How national policies can use SCORE results to fill gaps in climate adaptation and enhance resilience against sea-level risks.
EU level	Contributions to EU-wide strategies, particularly in relation to the directives described in section 4.

Table 3: Governance levels

5.2. Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA)

5.2.1 Description of outputs and tools

Socio-Economic Assessment of EBA in SCORE

Policymakers frequently encounter a lack of evidence on the potential impacts of adaptation strategies and measures, both during the decision-making process and in subsequent monitoring. Socio-economic assessment methods can provide reliable information to support well-grounded decisions. These methods are particularly valuable for capturing the multidimensional benefits of EBA and comparing them with other solutions. Beyond mitigating climate risks, EBA can also contribute to biodiversity conservation, air quality improvement, human health, and the support of recreational opportunities, among other benefits.

Socio-economic assessment methods are fundamental for making well-informed decisions regarding climate change adaptation. Effective decision-making relies on systematic information and data analysed by experts, as well as the incorporation of stakeholders' perspectives. The systematic literature review (check "D7.1-Synthesis of socio-economic assessment methods, databases, and studies addressing EBA and other adaptation strategies"¹⁸) undertaken by the SCORE consortium identified the most frequently used socio-economic methods for evaluating EBA and other measures.

Among these, **Multi-criteria Analysis (MCA)** was recognised as an optimal method for integrating knowledge and perspectives from a diverse range of stakeholders, including academia, public administration, the private sector, and civil society. This method enables a multidimensional, non-monetary evaluation of the potential benefits and constraints of adaptation solutions.

Additionally, **Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA)** emerged as a reliable, expert-based approach for assessing the economic efficiency of EBA measures. This method involves the monetary estimation of various factors, including investment and maintenance costs, as well as socio-economic and environmental benefits.

Both methods are described in SCORE's report "D7.2-Methodological Framework for the Socio-Economic Assessment of Adaptation Measures to Climate Change"¹⁹, a practical and accessible guide outlining the key steps for implementing the assessment approaches.

Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) in SCORE

MCA is a stakeholder-driven approach. The **advantages** of the MCA include the ability to evaluate various adaptation measures using a wide range of criteria, both quantitative and qualitative, without the need to monetise all factors. It can be easily adapted to different contexts through a straightforward approach that is based on the assignation of weighted and unweighted scores to the different criteria. Additionally, it facilitates the involvement of diverse stakeholders, including industry, academia, government, and civil society, thereby incorporating their perspectives and preferences into the analysis.

As for the **disadvantages**, the subjectivity in weighting the criteria can introduce bias into the assessment. Gathering and preparing all the necessary data and information to ensure participants are well informed, as well as recruiting

¹⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/11242253>

¹⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/11242292>

a representative and varied group of participants, can be time-consuming. Moreover, implementing the MCA can be complex when dealing with conflicting criteria.

How MCA Was Used in SCORE:

- Applied in the 10 SCORE CCLLs to prioritise the most beneficial EBA solutions for specific climate change hazards through participatory stakeholder engagement workshops, namely:
 - Oarsoaldea (Spain) – inland and coastal flooding, landslide, and heatwaves.
 - Piran (Slovenia) – coastal flooding, droughts, and heatwaves.
 - Sligo (Ireland) – coastal flooding.
 - Vilanova i la Geltrú/Province of Barcelona (Spain) – inland flooding.
 - Massa (Italy) – coastal flooding, storm surge, and heatwaves.
 - Dublin (Ireland) - coastal flooding, storm surge, and heatwaves.
 - Oeiras (Portugal) – inland flooding.
 - Gdansk (Poland) – inland flooding and storm surge.
 - Samsun (Turkey) – coastal erosion.
 - Benidorm (Spain) – inland and coastal flooding, and coastal erosion.
- Local policymakers, scientists, industry, and citizens assessed EBA measures based on the following criteria:
 - Environmental benefits (e.g. water retention, biodiversity conservation).
 - Risk reduction potential (e.g. flood mitigation, erosion control).
 - Economic feasibility (e.g. job creation).
 - Social acceptance and co-benefits (e.g. public health, recreational value).
- This method was carried out through the following steps: understanding the local adaptation context; identifying a list of preliminary EBA options; conducting a feasibility assessment of these options; defining evaluation criteria; assessment of measures using both unweighted and weighted criteria; and, finally, ranking and prioritizing the options.
- The top three prioritized measures across the CCLLs were:
 - Oarsoaldea (Spain) – green spaces, tree plantation, and riparian reforestation.
 - Piran (Slovenia) – restoration of historic wells and water reservoirs, sustainable permeable pavements, and green spaces.
 - Sligo (Ireland) – afforestation, peatland restoration, and wetland restoration.
 - Vilanova i la Geltrú/Province of Barcelona (Spain) – combination of measures (renaturing, restitution of the original riverbed depth, increase in riverbank height), renaturing and stabilization of riverbed and slopes, and restitution of riverbed depth.
 - Massa (Italy) – floodplain enlargement, riparian reforestation, and high-water channel.
 - Dublin (Ireland) – floodable park, saltmarsh restoration, and green infrastructure.

- Oeiras (Portugal) – planting indigenous vegetation, floodplain enlargement, and maintenance of the river network.
- Gdansk (Poland) – water parks and retention ponds, green spaces, and tree plantation.
- Samsun (Turkey) – floodplain enlargement, bank restoration/naturalization, and seagrass meadow introduction/restoration.
- Benidorm (Spain) – floodable park, riparian reforestation, and tree plantation.

The results of the MCA are available in the report “D7.3-Results from the participatory socio-economic assessment of EBA interventions²⁰.”

Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) in SCORE

CBA is a widely used expert-driven method that evaluates the financial efficiency of EBA measures by comparing investment costs with long-term socio-economic and environmental benefits, including ecosystem service provision and additional co-benefits. It provides decision-makers with a clear monetary justification for implementing NbS.

The **advantages** of this method include quantifying a broad spectrum of potential costs and benefits of adaptation measures in monetary terms, facilitating straightforward comparison of results. Additionally, it considers the long-term implications of the assessed measures by incorporating various climate change and socioeconomic scenarios, as well as discounting future costs and benefits.

As for the **disadvantages**, it is important to highlight the difficulty in quantifying intangible costs and benefits (such as the intrinsic value of nature), the uncertainty related to future predictions, the potential inaccuracy of long-term assumptions, and the risk of oversimplification by focusing solely on monetary metrics.

How CBA Was Used in SCORE:

- Applied in four frontrunner CCLLs—*Sligo, Piran, Oarsoaldea, Vilanova i la Geltrú*—as follows:
 - Errenteria, Oarsoaldea (Spain): An ex-post analysis was conducted for the period 2003-2044 to assess the role of an existing floodable park to mitigate flooding in the area, compared to an alternative scenario involving the construction of concrete walls to channel the river. The Net Present Value (NPV) of the intervention was calculated by considering avoided losses, highlighting the adaptation benefits.
 - Vilanova i la Geltrú (Catalonia, Spain): An ex-ante analysis was conducted to evaluate the impact of an intermittent river restoration strategy for flood mitigation, involving a combination of measures, including raising the height of the right riverbank with a levee in the form of an earthen embankment and widening the riverbed channel at selected cross-sections. The analysis covered the period 2024-2065, and the comparison of costs (investment and maintenance) and benefits (avoided losses) was made through the estimation of the NPV.
 - Piran (Slovenia): An ex-ante analysis was implemented to compare the costs and benefits of renovating and using historical water collection cisterns during drought periods, in contrast to alternative solutions such as water tanks and water trucks. Additionally, the CBA method was applied to the development of four green spaces in the old town and their role in mitigating the

²⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/14546380>

effects of heatwaves, among other benefits. Both analyses were conducted for a 42-year period starting in 2024, and evaluated costs and benefits of the respective measures through the NPV.

- Sligo County (Ireland): The analysis examined three beaches in County Sligo—Enniscrone, Strandhill, and Streedagh—by conducting a monetary valuation of the ecosystem services provided by their beach and dune areas, considering shoreline modelling projections for the period from 2024 to 2044. These services included coastal protection, carbon sequestration, and recreational benefits. Furthermore, the study provided a comparative overview of the costs associated with dune management and explored potential strategies for effective beach and dune conservation.
- Overall, the analyses showed that the assessed measures could serve as viable solutions for addressing local climate adaptation challenges. These measures offer not only hazard risk reduction and economic efficiency but also additional complementary benefits. By incorporating nature-based elements, they have the potential to deliver ecosystem services that are often overlooked in traditional grey infrastructure. However, achieving more effective climate change adaptation at the local level requires a hybrid approach, blending EBA with both hard and soft strategies.
- The results of the CBA are available in the report “D7.4-Results from the expert-based socio-economic assessment of EBA interventions” (Campos Rodrigues et al., 2025²¹).

EBA catalogue

The EBA Catalogue (<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/6cdbb2f6ab0744b89dffda2664dd877e>) developed within the SCORE project is an interactive tool designed to help users explore various EBA measures aimed at addressing climate change hazards, such as sea-level rise, flooding, coastal erosion, and storm surges, in both urban and natural coastal areas.

Key Features:

- Case Study Map Tour: Users can select different EBA options by clicking on map pinpoints, each providing detailed descriptions, objectives, benefits, and images related to the selected measure.
- Filter Functionality: The tool allows users to apply filters based on specific climate hazards and land typologies, enabling them to discover suitable adaptation options tailored to their needs.
- Interactive Global Map: A catalogue interactive map offers a global view of case study locations, illustrating where various EBA measures have been implemented.

The catalogue offers several key benefits for users and decision-makers. It enhances understanding by providing detailed case studies and visual representations, which help users grasp the scope and application of various EBA measures. It supports informed decision-making by offering filtering options and comprehensive information that enable policymakers, planners, and stakeholders to identify suitable adaptation strategies tailored to specific coastal challenges. Furthermore, the interactive map adds a global perspective that fosters knowledge sharing by showcasing a wide range of EBA implementations from different regions around the world.

²¹ Campos Rodrigues, L., Riera Spiegelhalder, M., Navarro, F., Arampatzis, S., Olympia, P., Tsiaras, G., Nalmpantis, D., Meulenber, C., Kralj, E., Kumer, P., Etxebarria, J., Iglesias, J., Soloaga, S., Undabeitia, A., Tiwari, A., Gharbia, S., Anton, I., Nalukurthi, S.-R., Riaz, K. (2025). D7.4-Results from the expert-based socio-economic assessment of EBA interventions. SCORE Project.

5.2.2. Recommendations at different levels

Local Level

Integrate EBA into Local Adaptation and Urban Planning Strategies

- Encourage municipalities to include EBA measures in Local Climate Adaptation Plans and coastal management strategies.
- SCORE Contribution: MCA assessments across 10 CCLLs ranked wetland restoration, sustainable drainage, and urban greening as high-priority adaptation solutions due to their multi-benefit impact. CBA in Sligo, Piran, Oarsoaldea, and Vilanova i la Geltrú demonstrated that EBA solutions—such as floodable parks, restoration of intermittent rivers, renovation of open-access green spaces and water cisterns, and beach and dune management—have the potential to deliver long-term savings. The direct benefits of these measures can outweigh their implementation and maintenance costs, mitigating climate hazards such as flooding and coastal erosion. In addition, they provide co-benefits including biodiversity conservation, carbon sequestration, and support for recreation and tourism.

Use MCA for community-informed EBA decision-making

- Local governments could incorporate MCA as a participatory tool in decision-making processes to reflect diverse community and expert perspectives on adaptation measures. Any participatory process should involve vulnerable communities as well. Attending for age and gender diversity should be also considered.
- SCORE Contribution: MCA was successfully applied in all 10 CCLLs, integrating local policymakers, scientists, industry, and citizens to assess EBA solutions.

Integrate MCA and then CBA in Local Climate Adaptation Planning

- Municipalities could systematically utilize MCA (or other participatory methods) to select few possible EBAs for the coastal area and then carry out CBA on those selected EBA solutions to ensure investments are cost-effective and aligned with local priorities.
- SCORE contribution: Conducting an MCA to prioritize EBA measures in the CCLLs, followed by a CBA of specific solutions, proved to be highly targeted and well-aligned with stakeholders' expectations. Note: Other methods could also be employed to effectively assess the proposed measures (see “D7.1- Synthesis of socio-economic assessment methods”²²).

Incorporate EBA solutions into the broader adaptation strategy

- Cities could prioritize EBA when CBA or other socioeconomic assessments demonstrate higher long-term financial and environmental returns compared to traditional engineered solutions considered for the same adaptation goals.
- Effective climate change adaptation at the local level requires a hybrid approach—one that integrates EBA with both hard measures (e.g. engineered infrastructure) and soft measures (e.g. monitoring systems, planning and prevention strategies).
- SCORE contribution: MCA and CBA in SCORE demonstrated that EBA have the potential to be an economically efficient approach, while also offering additional co-benefits that may not be achievable through engineering-based solutions.

²² <https://zenodo.org/records/11242253>

Educate local authorities on NbS and EBA measures

- Urban planners and environmental officers should be educated on coastal climate adaptation approaches, including NbS and EBA, to enable informed decision-making. This will allow them to recommend replacing hard engineering measures with EBA where appropriate or integrating the two approaches effectively.
- SCORE contribution: The EBA Catalogue's structured database can be adapted into a learning module for urban planners.

National Level

Encourage Socio-Economic Assessments for Climate Adaptation Investments

- Socio-economic assessments (such as MCA, CBA and others) should be encouraged for all types of climate adaptation investments, to help evaluate their effectiveness and ensure value for money. When it comes to EBA, such assessments can support the case for increased funding by highlighting long-term financial and environmental benefits. In parallel, national adaptation plans, often focused on larger-scale EBA initiatives, can require socio-economic assessments of EBA measures to understand their effectiveness in comparison to other adaptation options, before approving corresponding investments.
- SCORE Contribution: MCA and CBA across the various CCLLs demonstrated the potential for EBA measures to be economically efficient and provide additional social and environmental benefits (check the charts that show the economical amounts of the benefits in "D6.5 Risk profiles for the frontrunner CCLLs²³"). The EBA catalogue presents potential measures applicable to diverse geographical settings, which can be evaluated using the socio-economic methods reviewed and implemented in the SCORE project.

Create Dedicated National Climate Funds for EBA

- Governments should introduce dedicated Climate Resilience Funds, prioritizing grants and subsidies for wetland restoration, urban forests, and natural flood buffers.
- SCORE Contribution: SCORE demonstrated the economic benefits resulting from the EBA interventions (check the charts that show the economical amounts of the benefits in "D6.5 Risk profiles for the frontrunner CCLLs²⁴")

EU Level

Enhance NetworkNature (EU's flagship NbS knowledge platform <https://networknature.eu/>)

- Enhance Network Nature with harmonized assessment methodologies (like CBA, MCA and others) to ensure comparable socio-economic evaluations of EBA solutions across the EU.
- SCORE Contribution: The EBA Catalogue and socio-economic assessment framework (D7.1, D7.2) can support this action.

Enhance Climate-ADAPT (EU's platform in support to climate change adaptation <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/about/about-climate-adapt>)

²³ SCORE zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/score-eu-project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

²⁴ SCORE zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/score-eu-project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

- Enhance Climate-ADAPT with case studies focused on socioeconomic assessment of EBA measures
- SCORE contribution: SCORE D7.3 presents the participatory socio-economic assessment based on a MCA in the 10 CCLLs. The analysis focused on the prioritization of EBA measures to address different climate hazards (i.e., coastal and inland flooding, coastal erosion, droughts, heatwaves, and storm surges) across SCORE CCLLs.
- SCORE Contribution: SCORE D7.4 compares the costs and benefits of EBA measures in the four WP7 frontrunner CCLLs (a) comparison of a floodable park with an alternative river channelisation solution to mitigate flooding in Oarsoaldea, (b) evaluation of intermittent river restoration for flood mitigation in Vilanova i la Geltrú through an avoided cost approach, (c) assessment of the use of historic water cisterns for drought periods versus alternative solutions in Piran, (d) evaluation of the benefits of green spaces for heatwave mitigation in Piran, (e) examination of coastal erosion in Sligo with a monetary valuation of the ecosystem services provided by beach and dune areas.

Promote Transboundary EBA Cooperation for Shared Coastal Areas

- The EU should support cross-border adaptation programs, particularly for shared coastal regions affected by climate risks.
- SCORE Contribution: SCORE's MCA and co-creation methodologies support collaborative planning and governance across regions.

5.3 Coastal Cities Living Labs (CCLLs)

5.3.1 Description of outputs and tools

CCLL Framework

CCLLs are defined as real-life, collaborative environments where diverse stakeholders work together to co-create, test, implement, and evaluate solutions for climate resilience and adaptation. Inspired by the work done by the European Network of Living Labs (ENOLL), which enhances scalability and adaptability, we highlight the importance of CCLLs in creating networks and enhancing localised solutions. However, we also identify challenges, such as complexity of coordination and managing co-creation, when designing and implementing a CCLL framework. Below we refer to some strategies and success stories from our partner cities and regions to illustrate the transformative potential and practical considerations of CCLLs.

Our CCLL approach represents a transformative shift in governance and decision-making, fostering a collaborative, inclusive, and holistic framework. Traditional governance models have often limited key stakeholders' participation, particularly in the early phases of identifying problems and designing solutions. By contrast, the CCLL model proposed in the SCORE project actively brings together actors from the quadruple helix (academia, industry, government, and civil society) promoting that each phase is co-created and informed by diverse expertise and perspectives. This inclusive participatory approach not only enhances the relevance and acceptability of the solutions developed, but it also promotes more responsive and resilient solutions, deeply rooted in the unique needs, insights and values of local stakeholders.

Within the SCORE project, a network of 10 CCLLs has been established across the following European coastal cities:

- Sligo, Ireland
- Dublin, Ireland
- Oeiras, Portugal
- Barcelona Province/Vilanova i la Geltrú, Spain
- Benidorm, Spain
- Oarsoaldea, Spain
- Gdańsk, Poland
- Piran, Slovenia
- Samsun, Turkey
- Massa, Italy

CCLLs are inspired by ENOLL definition of Living Labs as "real-life, collaborative environments designed for the co-creation, testing, implementation, and evaluation of solutions with active stakeholder involvement". Clearly defining the CCLL concept helps build a shared understanding of the purpose and structure of CCLLs among stakeholders. A unified definition reinforces the integrity and focus of CCLLs, fostering a consistent approach across various cities and regions and enhancing collaboration.

CCLLs foster connections among like-minded, committed individuals to create movement and foster momentum around local climate resilience efforts. Strong, trusting relationships are essential for CCLL success. Key takeaways from SCORE CCLLs experiences include:

- Finding local champions: Consistent core stakeholders, particularly from local and regional governments, are essential for fostering engagement and strengthening commitment within the community.
- Support from larger institutions: Provincial and regional governments can significantly aid in scaling co-creation efforts by connecting CCLLs with broader communities or in connecting with other initiatives, thereby amplifying their impact.

CCLLs enable the development and co-creation of locally embedded solutions. By tailoring solutions to place-specific environmental issues and climate challenges, CCLLs foster solutions that are relevant and sustainable. Some strategies by the CCLLs include the following:

- Use participatory tools and methods: Methods such as MCA for assessing EBA or citizen science activities enable a diverse range of perspectives, which enhances the co-creation process.
- Validated and socially accepted solutions: Engaging stakeholders from the quadruple helix in every phase of the Living Lab process from the identification of the challenges, the co-design of solutions and decision-making process, the implemented solutions gain broader support and acceptance. This inclusive approach helps reduce resistance to the adopted measures.
- Addressing resource constraints: To overcome limitations in resources, CCLLs actively seek new projects, explore diverse funding sources, develop a service portfolio they can offer to potential clients, and build strategic partnerships. Establishing a shared understanding of the Living Lab model through the ENoLL definition can further strengthen these networks, creating clarity on the purpose and structure of CCLLs.

Differentiating between Living Labs established at a macro level (broad, systemic initiatives embedded in an organisation) and projects using the Living Lab methodology (focused, time-bound projects targeting specific challenges) provides policymakers and practitioners with a clearer view of the scalability and adaptability of the Living Lab methodology. This distinction is particularly crucial for addressing complex, multifaceted issues that resist simple solutions and require collaborative, iterative approaches. By clarifying these distinctions, the methodology can be better aligned with local needs and resources, promoting a flexible and responsive approach to tackling climate adaptation and other complex urban challenges. This clarity enables cities and regions to determine whether to integrate Living Labs as large-scale, systemic initiatives or apply the methodology to specific, localized challenges, ensuring a more targeted and impactful solution to pressing issues.

CCLLs involves a wide range of stakeholders with varying priorities, knowledge levels, and availability, which can create coordination and long-term engagement challenges. To streamline operations and maintain active involvement, the following strategies are recommended:

- Structured process: Dividing the framework into clear phases and steps enables better synchronisation of stakeholder efforts, making participation more organized and manageable. Following a framework such as the [Living Lab Integrative Process](#), is recommended.
- Pilot Operational plans: Clearly defining roles, responsibilities, and priorities, while using interactive digital platforms and regular workshops, keeps stakeholders connected, engaged, and invested throughout the project. The POP is a structured guide that ensures the development and establishment of a LL over a fixed period, focusing specifically on stakeholder engagement and panel management. The POP provides LLs with a structured approach and framework to setting up and running a LL project, while taking steps to ensure

the sustainability of the LL. The POP was adapted into a [template](#) to be used broadly by any Living Lab. More information <https://score-eu-project.eu/tools-and-platforms/>.

Co-creation toolkit

The co-creation in CCLLs is inherently a time-consuming and resource intensive process. To support efficient collaboration among stakeholders, SCORE has developed a comprehensive digital [Co-Creation toolkit](#) (see resources) that supports stakeholders in navigating the co-creation process more effectively, reducing complexity and facilitating smoother collaboration.

In addition, an online course “How to Establish a Living Lab (with Lessons learned)” is currently under development. This course provides step-by-step guidance on setting up a Living Lab, including lessons learned from past initiatives. It can be a valuable resource for cities looking to adopt the CCLL approach, supporting knowledge sharing and capacity building across regions.

Monitoring and evaluation

The SCORE CCLL Monitoring and Evaluation framework was applied across all ten CCLLs within the SCORE project. Grounded in established Monitoring and Evaluation approaches for LLs and incorporating participatory Monitoring and Evaluation principles, the framework evaluates both process (implementation) and effect (outcome/impact). The process evaluation assesses how activities are managed and whether they are implemented as intended, while the outcome evaluation measures the results and effects within each CCLL. Participatory Monitoring and Evaluation is a core feature, emphasizing stakeholder involvement in assessing progress and effectiveness, ensuring a more inclusive and reflective evaluation process.

By providing a structured assessment, the framework addresses the lack of a standardized evaluation approach, which currently limits cross-project learning and scalability. However, further refinement and adaptation can enhance its effectiveness for broader applications. A uniform evaluation framework would enable cross-project comparisons, offering deeper insights into the contexts where LLs are most impactful. It would also serve as a guiding tool for participants, particularly those unfamiliar with LL concepts, by supporting them through the development, implementation, and evaluation phases. Beyond EU-funded initiatives, a standardized Monitoring and Evaluation approach could facilitate the wider adoption of LLs by providing a structured, replicable model, strengthening their role in advancing climate resilience and urban innovation. Please check the deliverable related to Monitoring and Evaluation “D2.3 Evaluation outcomes and sustainability plans of CCLLs²⁵”.

5.3.2. Recommendations at different levels

Local Level

Integrate CCLLs into local climate strategies, urban development plans and infrastructure design

- Local governments should formally embed the CCLL model within their urban planning and climate adaptation strategies. Use participatory tools, such as MCA, co-creation toolkit and citizen science, to prioritize and validate ecosystem-based adaptation solutions.

²⁵ SCORE zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/score-eu-project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

- SCORE Contribution: The SCORE project demonstrated that sustained engagement through CCLs, such as in Sligo, Dublin, and Massa, allowed for place-based, stakeholder-driven solutions that were both more relevant and more broadly supported. The use of participatory tools like MCA and citizen science ensured that adaptation measures were socially accepted and technically feasible. Municipalities can adopt SCORE's Co-Creation Toolkit and forthcoming online Living Lab course to operationalise the Living Lab model, helping institutional actors coordinate better across departments and with the public.

Ensure cross-sectoral collaboration in CCLs

- Local authorities should mandate the participation of urban planning, environment, and economic development stakeholders in CCLs.
- SCORE Contribution: The quadruple helix model used by SCORE for stakeholder engagement frameworks in WP2 ensured that municipalities, businesses, academia and civil society were active in co-creation processes.

Expand funding opportunities for municipal Living Labs

- Introduce municipal grants and tax incentives to sustain CCLs as permanent innovation hubs for climate adaptation. Secure funding from local budgets and public-private partnerships (PPPs) to sustain Living Lab operations over time.
- SCORE Contribution: SCORE highlighted the need for sustainable funding models, particularly in Fellow CCLs (Benidorm, Dublin, Gdańsk, Massa, Oeiras, Samsun) which faced financial constraints.

Adopt standardized monitoring and evaluation frameworks for CCLs

- Cities should develop Key performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure the success of CCLs in enhancing climate resilience and stakeholder engagement.
- SCORE Contribution: WP2 developed a Monitoring and evaluation strategy that assessed CCLs' long-term impact and stakeholder engagement success (see "D2.3 Evaluation outcomes and sustainability plans of CCLs²⁶").

National Level

Recognize Living Labs as key innovation instruments in national climate strategies

- National adaptation plans should include CCLs as formal governance tools for testing and implementing EBA.
- SCORE Contribution: The Living Lab methodology in WP2 has shown that CCLs enhance the effectiveness of EBA and climate governance. SCORE also emphasized the importance of cross-city collaboration, particularly between Frontrunner and Fellow CCLs.

Establish national funding programs for CCLs

- National governments should create dedicated climate innovation funds that support the establishment and scaling of CCLs.

²⁶ SCORE zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/score-eu-project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

- SCORE Contribution: The SCORE Pilot Operational Plans (D2.1, D2.2) outlined strategies for securing long-term funding beyond EU projects.

Enhance national capacity-building programs for Living Labs

- Governments could incentivize the development of training programs for policymakers and municipal planners on how to implement and sustain Living Labs for climate adaptation.
- SCORE Contribution: The SCORE project has documented success stories and best practices from 10 CCLLs that can inform national training programs. SCORE has also developed courses within the MOOC that could be applicable here <https://score-eu-project.eu/online-courses/>

EU Level

Integrate Living Labs into EU Climate Adaptation Policy

- The EU Adaptation Strategy, related directives (e.g. Flood Directive, Marine Strategy Framework Directive) and Horizon Europe Missions (ex. Mission: 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030) should explicitly recognize Living Labs as formal innovation ecosystems. Include CCLLs as a pillar of EU-funded programs to enhance citizen engagement in climate policy development.
- SCORE Contribution: SCORE demonstrated that CCLLs serve as effective tools for co-creation and stakeholder-driven climate solutions. Use the CCLL Knowledge & Lessons Learned Guide to inform EU directives on participatory governance.

Foster Knowledge exchange among Coastal City Living Labs

- Foster knowledge exchange between European cities and not only, and projects to share lessons learned from the Living Lab models.
- SCORE Contribution: The SCORE project demonstrated that CCLLs facilitate transnational collaboration on coastal climate resilience.

5.4 Participatory and Citizen Science Approaches

5.4.1 Description of outputs and tools

Community Geosurveys platform (geosurveys.score-eu-project.eu)

The SCORE Community Geosurveys platform is a customizable mapping platform (based on the CartoSpot software) that enables participatory monitoring through citizen contributed data. It allows users to create their own map-based surveys to visualise and report on local climate-related issues. This enhances real-time data collection and provides decision-makers with localised insights into environmental impacts.

There was a need for more flexible and interactive tools that allow citizens to actively participate in environmental monitoring. Existing systems were either too rigid or failed to engage local communities effectively. The platform addresses these gaps by enabling citizens to design and use surveys that capture local climate issues in real time.

The platform is highly customizable, allowing for adaptable surveys to suit different regions and climate issues or topics. It empowers local communities to contribute data in the form of text and images, leading to more immediate and context-specific information for decisionmakers.

The platform can support Flood Directive by enabling communities to report flood risks/events in real time. It also aligns with the EU Climate Change Adaptation Strategy by involving citizens in ongoing environmental monitoring efforts.

However, successful implementation requires internet access and a basic level of digital literacy, potentially excluding some groups. Additionally, the quality of the data could vary if citizen input is not adequately moderated.

Low-cost sensors catalogue (<https://sensors.score-eu-project.eu>)

The Low-Cost Sensor Catalogue is a review of affordable sensors for environmental monitoring in alignment with the identified priorities and climate hazards in the SCORE CCLLs. It identifies cost-effective technologies that can be deployed in community-led climate adaptation initiatives, making high quality data collection accessible to a broader audience.

The high cost of traditional environmental monitoring technology has been a barrier to widespread monitoring, particularly in underfunded areas and resource limited contexts. The catalogue addresses this by identifying more affordable alternatives, enabling broader data collection for climate monitoring efforts. Those affordable and accessible sensors increase participation in environmental monitoring and can provide high density data on climate impacts. They are ideal for use in resource-limited regions.

However, low-cost sensors often have reduced accuracy and durability compared to higher-end authoritative models. Data from such devices may require additional validation processes or expert attention.

Citizen science Playbook (guidance for engaging citizens in Living labs co-monitoring activities)

The “D4.1 Citizen Science Playbook²⁷” together with the “D4.5 Citizen science activities in CCLs²⁸” and “D4.6 Validation of citizen science data²⁹” provide a structured engagement framework for involving communities in environmental monitoring. With the Citizen Science Playbook offering learning modules for principal climate adaptive knowledge transfer that guide co-monitoring activities, making citizen engagement more accessible, transparent, and systematic. They promote inclusivity in data collection for climate change adaptation and environmental management through bottom-up citizen led initiatives.

These deliverables address the lack of effective public participation in monitoring environmental issues and the limitations of current practices. The gap between formal scientific research and local knowledge can often hinder adaptive responses to climate hazards. Through the involvement of citizens, the Playbook bridges this gap, creating a more comprehensive toolset when it comes to environmental monitoring projects.

The Playbook fosters community ownership of climate monitoring, leading to more sustained engagement. It also builds trust between local populations and public institutions/municipalities, while also enhancing data diversity and coverage. Hence, it provides significant investment in training and public engagement/motivation through learning modules, while together these deliverables provide guidelines to prevent inconsistent data quality as provided by non-experts, and guidelines for citizen science data validation.

Geodesign game (<https://score-eu-project.eu/geodesign-game>)

The SCORE Geodesign Game is an interactive digital platform developed to simulate urban planning scenarios, enabling participants to assume various roles and collaboratively design and implement EBAs. Rooted in Geodesign and serious gaming principles, the game facilitates participatory spatial decision-making by addressing conflicting perspectives and promoting collaboration. Participants work together to propose, discuss, and vote on EBA solutions tailored to their region's specific ecological, social, and economic needs. This process encourages inclusive decision-making and fosters innovative, community-driven solutions for sustainable development. It simplifies complex climate planning by providing a visual and interactive platform that fosters informed decision-making. Additionally, it supports scenario testing, enabling policymakers to explore multiple adaptation options before real-world implementation.

However, the game requires structured facilitation and training for participants, as some stakeholders may struggle with digital tools or geospatial concepts. Data accuracy and availability are crucial, as unreliable inputs could lead to misleading conclusions. Furthermore, time constraints and digital accessibility issues may limit participation, especially among marginalized communities or less tech-savvy users.

Citizen science framework

The SCORE Citizen Science Framework provides a structured approach to engaging local communities in environmental monitoring and climate resilience efforts. It empowers citizens to collect real-time data using low-

²⁷ SCORE zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/score-eu-project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

²⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/13960815>

²⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/13960853>

cost sensors, geospatial surveys, and digital tools, integrating this information into the SCORE Sensor Things API (API: Application Programming Interface) for decision-making. The framework includes training workshops, a DIY onboarding platform, and the Citizen Science Playbook, ensuring that non-experts can contribute effectively to scientific research and local adaptation planning.

By combining community-driven data collection with institutional validation, the framework enhances participatory governance and evidence-based policymaking. It fosters collaboration between citizens, scientists, and policymakers, ensuring wider public engagement in climate adaptation. Ultimately, this model helps coastal cities build more inclusive and resilient adaptation strategies, strengthening early-warning systems and local policy interventions.

The main citizen science activities in each CCLL that back up the following recommendations can be found in “D4.5 Citizen Science activities in CCLL³⁰”.

5.4.2. Recommendations at different levels

Local Level

Integrate citizen science into local climate adaptation planning

- Local governments could be encouraged to utilize the Community Geosurveys platform for mapping climate risks (e.g. flood zones, heat islands) with real-time community input. They could also mandate the use of citizen-collected data from the platform in climate adaptation strategies.
- SCORE Contribution: The Geosurveys platform has been successfully tested in CCLLs, engaging citizens in co-monitoring coastal risks. The SCORE Sensor Things API demonstrated how local authorities can validate and use citizen-contributed data

Facilitate adoption of low-cost sensors for community-led monitoring

- Local governments could establish municipal funding schemes to equip communities with low-cost environmental sensors. This will enhance the efficiency of coastal climate data monitoring (in variables such as air quality, temperature, and water levels), thereby informing climate policy.
- SCORE Contribution: The Low-cost Sensors Catalogue provided municipalities with affordable, effective monitoring technologies. Local partners have worked with local citizen science groups to deploy and manage these sensors effectively.

Use participatory planning games for co-designed adaptation measures

- Cities could integrate the Geodesign Game into public consultations and urban resilience workshops as a participatory tool to actively involve stakeholders in the decision-making process. It can also support building consensus around potential conflicts and exploring collaboratively developed solutions.
- SCORE Contribution: The Geodesign Game has been tested in CCLLs to facilitate stakeholder collaboration and scenario planning. The game sessions were adapted to their specific local areas and conducted in their

³⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/13960815>

local languages. In addition to testing within the SCORE network, the game has also been tested with external communities to further assess its usability and adaptability in real-life applications.

Provide Training and Resources for Citizen Scientists

- Local governments should allocate funding for training programs that teach residents how to collect and interpret environmental data. Organize workshops to educate communities on the Citizen Science Playbook and its practical applications in co-monitoring climate hazards such as flooding and heatwaves. Ensure citizen science tools are accessible to vulnerable communities, providing training on digital platforms and sensor use.
- **SCORE Contribution:** The DIY onboarding platform and Citizen Science Playbook provide structured guidance for community engagement. SCORE is also developing a citizen science course to be ready in June 2025 to support local governments.

National Level

Establish national citizen science frameworks

- Governments should develop standardized protocols for integrating citizen-generated data into formal monitoring frameworks and environmental decision-making. Integrate the platform into national climate monitoring frameworks, ensuring data from local communities feeds into national-level decision-making processes.
- **SCORE Contribution:** SCORE demonstrated the value of participatory monitoring through tools like the Citizen Science DIY Framework (D4.3³¹), the Low-Cost Sensor Catalogue, and the Citizen Science Playbook, which offer practical guidance for data accuracy and integration. The Community Geosurveys platform bridges gaps in policy by enabling spatially-referenced, citizen-generated data collection. Together, these tools showcase the viability of low-cost, community-led monitoring and highlight the need for supportive national policies and infrastructure.

Expand training programs for policymakers and civil servants

- National agencies should include citizen science methodologies in climate governance training programs.
- **SCORE Contribution:** WP4 developed educational resources for municipal officials, schools, and local organizations.

EU Level

Promote digital citizen science literacy across Member States

- The EU should fund training programs to enhance public participation in data-driven climate policies.
- **SCORE Contribution:** The project's EBA Training Schools have already provided educational support for citizen science engagement.

³¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/11242108>

Develop an EU-Wide Digital Platform for Citizen Science Data

- The European Environment Agency (EEA) should establish a centralized repository for validated citizen-collected environmental data, supporting EU-wide policymaking.
- SCORE Contribution: The SCORE Sensor Things API demonstrated the feasibility of integrating citizen science data into official decision-making.

Integrate citizen science into EU climate adaptation policies

- The EU Climate Change Adaptation Strategy and related directives should formally recognize citizen science as a valuable tool for climate risk assessment, environmental monitoring, and community-based resilience. Citizen-generated data should be integrated into key EU policies such as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), Floods Directive, and the EU Biodiversity Strategy, ensuring it informs both planning and response.
- SCORE Contribution: SCORE's tools developed under WP4 directly support this integration. The Citizen Science Playbook provides structured guidance for embedding citizen-generated data into decision-making, aligning with the EU Adaptation and Biodiversity Strategies. The Community Geosurveys platform enables real-time, spatially referenced reporting of climate risks (e.g. Flooding) supporting objectives under the Floods Directive. Additionally, the Low-Cost Sensor Catalogue facilitates large-scale, affordable environmental monitoring, contributing to the EU's goal of scaling adaptive measures through inclusive, local engagement.

5.5 Financial Resilience and Risk Management Tools

5.5.1 Description of outputs and tools

Methodology for assessing climate risk for European coastal cities

A standardized and systematic approach for comparing climate-related hazards across European coastal cities remains lacking due to the complexity of climate risks and challenges related to data availability. The SCORE methodology for climate risk assessment addresses this gap by integrating hazard, exposure, and vulnerability factors to establish a baseline risk analysis for European coastal cities.

This approach evaluates historical climate events, geospatial data, and stakeholder input from 10 CCLLs to develop risk maps and identify climate vulnerability hotspots. It considers multiple hazards, including coastal erosion, coastal and land flooding, landslides, strong winds, and heatwaves. The methodology relies on GIS-based spatial analysis and a semi-quantitative risk scoring system, where indicators are weighted to assess sensitivity and adaptive capacity.

For each CCLL, the methodology includes:

- Baseline Risk Maps assessing current climate risks in a semi-quantitative manner.
- Identification of Key Hazards, such as coastal flooding, erosion, and heatwaves.
- Mapping of Risk Hotspots based on historical events and spatial vulnerability analysis.

Key risks identified across coastal cities include sea-level rise, storm surges, and an increased frequency of extreme weather events, leading to coastal and land flooding, infrastructure damage, and ecosystem loss. Heatwaves also pose growing threats, particularly in southern European regions. By combining hazard model outputs, historical disaster data, and vulnerability indices, this methodology enables policymakers to prioritize adaptation measures more effectively.

One of the primary strengths of this methodology is its scientific rigor combined with practical applicability, making it a valuable tool for researchers, policymakers, and urban planners. It offers comprehensive coverage of climate-related hazards, including sea-level rise, coastal flooding, erosion, extreme weather events, and droughts, making it a robust framework for large-scale, high-level risk assessments. Additionally, its scalability and adaptability allow it to be applied to any European coastal city, enabling comparative baseline analyses and fostering collaborative resilience-building efforts. The methodology follows an indicator-based approach, meaning its results can be continuously refined as more accurate data and advanced climate models become available.

In conclusion, this methodology provides a strong foundation for preliminary assessments of climate risks in coastal cities. However, its effectiveness depends on continued improvements in data quality, methodological refinement, and capacity-building efforts to ensure its accessibility and usability across different governance levels. By integrating climate science, spatial analysis, and socioeconomic data, this scalable and comprehensive methodology serves as a robust decision-support tool for policymakers. Through the use of cutting-edge climate datasets and participatory urban resilience strategies, it aims to strengthen long-term adaptive planning in vulnerable coastal regions.

Quantitative Risk assessment

SCORE provides a comprehensive, quantitative risk assessment framework for European coastal cities. The combined data-driven approach allows authorities and decision-makers to visualize, assess, and mitigate financial risks associated with climate hazards, particularly coastal and fluvial flooding. The framework integrates the following components:

INPUT DATA

Flood hazard modelling: Hazard maps for each CCLL were produced for fluvial and coastal flooding considering five different climate scenarios: historical baseline, RCP4.5 2015-2065, RCP4.5 2045-2095, RCP8.5 2015-2065, and RCP8.5 2045-2095. Furthermore, in the case of fluvial flooding, two situations were modelled in terms of hazard mitigation measures, namely with and without the presence of EBAs. For each scenario, the hazard dataset comprises flood maps for six return periods: 5, 25, 50, 100, 200 and 500 years. This amounts to a total of 60 fluvial flood hazard maps and 30 coastal flood hazard maps for each CCLL. The selection of fluvial flooding to assess the impact of the EBAs resulted from discussions between different project stakeholders. This included a participatory process in which the three frontrunner CCLLs identified the main issues that should be addressed in the context of the SCORE project.

Exposure Database: A geospatial dataset mapping assets, infrastructure, and populations at risk.

- Identifies critical infrastructure (roads, buildings, transport systems) and vulnerable populations. It was used to provide spatial mapping of exposed elements in three frontrunners CCLLs (Massa, Oarsoaldea, and Vilanova i la Geltrú).
- By generating a comprehensive database of infrastructure and population elements exposed to climate hazards in coastal cities, it enables the estimation of potential damage with geographic localization. This allows for a clear visualization of areas most affected by river flooding, providing policymakers with crucial insights on where preventive actions should be prioritized.
- Supports scenario-based risk evaluation, including historical data and future climate projections (RCP 8.5, 2045-2095).
- During the creation of the exposure database for infrastructure elements, SCORE team encountered significant variations in format and information structure at the local level, particularly for buildings. Addressing this required substantial efforts to standardize the data, which was successfully achieved using various computational and mathematical tools.

Replacement costs: Estimated financial value required to repair or replace assets (e.g. buildings, transport infrastructure, and other critical elements) that are damaged due to flooding or other climate-related hazards. For the estimation of the replacement costs of the exposed elements in the frontrunner CCLLs, European studies and RED's internal database of replacement unit costs were used as a reference to provide an appropriate monetary dimension. The latter has been developed over the years based on multiple sources that include detailed construction cost data, construction market survey data, and analyses of technical documentation, reports, and scientific literature. Nevertheless, the replacement cost estimates may be updated with references to the local level of each city, which would result in an approximation with a lower degree of uncertainty.

Vulnerability Curves: Quantitative models estimating the degree of damage to different assets based on hazard intensity (e.g. flood depth).

- Developed for buildings, transport infrastructure, and human settlements.
- Uses standardized, state of the art damage estimation models (e.g. INSYDE, JRC depth-damage functions).
 - Quantifies economic and structural damage for varying flood scenarios.

OUTPUTS

Risk Profiles: Summarized assessments of potential flood impacts, economic losses, and affected populations, supporting evidence-based policy decisions.

- Offers graphical and statistical summaries of risk levels across the CCLLs.
- Includes flood hazard maps, exceedance probability curves, and annual economic loss estimates.
- Compares current conditions vs. future adaptation scenarios, highlighting the effectiveness of EBAs.

The resulting risk profiles for each city are visually summarized through maps, illustrating the concentration and distribution of exposed elements within each frontrunner CCLL. These maps highlight areas at the highest risk of flooding under different probabilities of occurrence and future climate scenarios. They also provide localized impact estimates and compare potential losses between the current situation and a scenario where mitigation measures, based on an ecosystem-based adaptation approach, are implemented.

Financial resilience strategies and decision support tool to address residual risks

SCORE provides a structured approach to financial risk management for coastal cities dealing with flooding and other climate hazards, through:

Financial Resilience Strategies: A framework of layered financial mechanisms that help local authorities manage the economic impact of residual risks (i.e. climate-related risks that persist even after adaptation measures are applied). In the context of SCORE, the financial resilience strategies aimed at managing the financial risk related to floods (both fluvial and coastal) for the three frontrunner CCLLs (Massa, Oarsoaldea and Vilanova i la Geltrú)

- Developed through historical "as-if" cash flow simulations, these strategies enable cities to assess potential economic losses under different climate scenarios. The cash flow diagrams outline how the cash balance of a potential municipal disaster risk management fund would have varied had the hypothesised financial strategies been implemented, helping policymakers understand financial sustainability and ROI (Return on Investment).
- The financial strategies include:
 - Risk Retention Mechanisms: such as reserve funds for high-frequency, low-impact events.
 - Risk Transfer Mechanisms: such as insurance models for low-frequency, high-impact disasters.
 - Blended finance approaches: encouraging cities to combine public funds, EU grants, and private investments to support long-term adaptation initiatives
- A 20,000-year Monte Carlo simulation was conducted to optimize strategy performance, balancing financial costs with expected residual losses.
- A set of risk management decision support guidelines will be also produced for policymakers.

Decision Support Tool: It is a user-friendly digital platform designed to assist policymakers in selecting optimal financial strategies based on cost-effectiveness and long-term resilience outcomes. Developed using estimations of residual risk and local historical damage cost data, the tool helps visualize different solution alternatives to minimize the financial impact of natural hazards. Specifically designed for local governments and policymakers, it employs a Pareto-optimal approach, enabling users to balance insurance costs, reserve fund allocation, and uncovered residual losses. By providing interactive visualizations of financial trade-offs, the tool allows cities to make data-driven decisions on resilience investments. Through a comparative analysis of potential solutions, it presents a

structured evaluation of different financial strategies, detailing the associated costs and benefits to support informed decision-making. Integrated cash flow modelling further enhances financial planning, helping cities optimize strategies to mitigate disaster-related losses. Ultimately, the tool enables decision-makers to systematically balance costs and benefits, reducing residual risk and strengthening financial preparedness against climate hazards. This output directly supports coastal city decision-makers in evaluating, comparing, and implementing financial mechanisms to enhance climate resilience.

5.5.2. Recommendations at different levels

Local Level

Encourage local authorities to implement comprehensive risk assessment frameworks

- Local authorities should adopt integrated risk assessment frameworks that account for both natural and human-induced factors affecting coastal areas. This holistic approach enables the identification of multiple hazards and supports more resilient urban planning and development.
- SCORE Contribution: SCORE developed Baseline Risk Maps and Risk Hotspots for 10 CCLs, enabling cities to prioritize adaptation interventions based on localized risk profiles. A GIS-based, semi-quantitative risk scoring system was introduced, offering flexibility to adapt to varying levels of data availability and governance contexts. By integrating diverse datasets and methodologies, SCORE demonstrated the value of a multi-dimensional risk perspective that can be embedded in municipal strategic plans, zoning policies, and development decisions.

Promote active involvement of stakeholders

- Local communities, businesses, and civil society actors should be actively involved in the development and implementation of risk management strategies. Their participation ensures that policies are rooted in local realities, increase social acceptance, and benefit from diverse knowledge and perspectives. Engaging stakeholders in participatory risk mapping and the validation of vulnerability hotspots enhances the accuracy, relevance, and legitimacy of adaptation measures.
- SCORE Contribution: Through the CCLs, SCORE implemented participatory processes that engaged a wide range of local stakeholders in risk assessment, data validation, and co-creation of solutions. These efforts demonstrated that stakeholder involvement is critical for the acceptance, effectiveness, and long-term sustainability of risk management measures.

Develop Municipal Reserve Funds for Climate Risks

- Local governments should establish dedicated climate resilience reserve funds to provide financial security against frequent but low-impact climate events. These funds should be structured to cover emergency response, infrastructure repairs, and pre-emptive adaptation measures. Localized baseline risk maps can also guide investment in resilience infrastructure.
- SCORE Contribution: The SCORE Financial Resilience Strategies identified risk retention mechanisms, such as municipal reserve funds, as effective tools for managing high-frequency, low-impact climate risks.

Adopt Risk Transfer Mechanisms for Large-Scale Disasters

- Municipalities should implement climate risk insurance schemes and collaborate with private insurers to cover low-frequency, high-impact disasters like coastal floods and storm surges. These mechanisms help distribute financial risks and prevent municipalities from bearing unsustainable recovery costs.
- SCORE Contribution: The SCORE Decision Support Tool illustrated the applicability of combining risk retention and risk transfer mechanisms such as insurance in reducing residual financial risks, using the frontrunners CCLs of Massa, Oarsoaldea, and Vilanova i la Geltrú as examples.

Integrate Financial Risk Assessments into Urban Planning

- Municipalities should integrate financial risk assessments into their urban planning frameworks to ensure that future investments in infrastructure are climate-resilient. This involves using GIS-based risk assessment tools to identify high-risk areas and prioritize adaptation investments.
- SCORE Contribution: The SCORE Risk Assessment and Risk Profiles provided georeferenced risk maps and vulnerability curves, helping cities quantify economic risks under different climate scenarios.

National Level

Standardization of Climate Risk Assessment

- Establish national guidelines for integrating hazard, exposure, and vulnerability indicators into regional planning.
- SCORE Contribution: SCORE demonstrated scalability and adaptability of the risk assessment methodology, allowing its application across various regional contexts.

Create National Disaster Risk Financing Strategies

- National governments should develop integrated disaster risk financing strategies that support municipalities in managing climate-related financial risks. These strategies should combine public funds, insurance mechanisms, and private sector contributions to strengthen overall financial resilience.
- SCORE Contribution: The Monte Carlo simulation conducted in SCORE optimized financial resilience strategies by balancing insurance costs, reserve fund allocation, and expected residual losses.

Enhance Public-Private Partnerships for Climate Finance

- National policies should encourage public-private partnerships (PPPs) to fund climate adaptation projects. This can include incentives for private sector investments in climate-resilient infrastructure and nature-based solutions.
- SCORE Contribution: The SCORE blended finance approach demonstrated the effectiveness of combining public funds, EU grants, and private investments to support long-term adaptation initiatives.

Implement Nationwide Climate Risk Stress Testing for Public Investments

- Governments should require climate risk stress testing for large-scale public investments to ensure financial sustainability under future climate conditions. This should be integrated into national budgeting processes and fiscal planning frameworks.
- SCORE Contribution: The SCORE Risk Profiles provided quantitative assessments of expected economic losses due to climate risks, serving as a basis for stress testing investment portfolios.

EU Level

EU-Wide Framework for Coastal Climate Risk Assessment

- Standardize risk assessment methodologies across Member States to align with EU directives.
- SCORE Contribution: SCORE delivered a robust, scalable, and indicator-based risk assessment methodology aligning with EU resilience policies. Demonstrated cross-country applicability by engaging 10 diverse CCLs from different Member States in a unified methodological framework. Provided quantitative risk profiles and mapping tools supporting EU policy objectives.

Standardize Climate Risk Reporting and Financial Disclosure

- The EU should require climate-related financial disclosures for public and private sector investments to increase transparency and improve risk-informed decision-making.
- SCORE Contribution: The SCORE Risk Profiles and Decision Support Tool highlighted the need for standardized financial reporting on climate risks, which helps decision-makers allocate resources more effectively.

Promote Insurance Market Reforms for Climate Resilience

- The EU should introduce regulatory incentives for insurance companies to expand coverage for climate risks, including parametric insurance models for coastal flooding and extreme weather events.
- SCORE Contribution: The SCORE financial resilience framework identified climate risk insurance as a key tool for reducing economic vulnerability and ensuring rapid post-disaster recovery.

5.6 Data collection, downscaling and modelling

5.6.1 Description of outputs and tools

Creation of hazard flooding maps

Enhancing urban resilience to climate change requires high-resolution hazard evaluation tools. The SCORE project has developed an innovative package of methodologies and models for downscaling climate data and simulating urban-scale hazards. These models use large-scale climate products-available through selected European data services, which are open and reliable - to produce high resolution and localized data (resolution of ten meters or less). This refinement is essential for urban applications bridging the gap between global and regional climate models (GCMs and RCMs, which have a resolution of tens of kilometers) and the detailed and specific data (resolution of hundreds of meters) needed for resilience planning at the "everyday life" scale, i.e., for feeding the urban scale models (resolution of few meters). The process starts from regional climate projections of atmosphere and sea and nest hydrodynamic, wave, and hydrological models that solve the finer scale. Their outputs are integrated within a statistical framework, so that these tools and methodologies provide outputs for 'last-mile' urban-scale models (e.g. HEC-RAS, FUNWAVE, XBEACH) to produce precise flood hazard maps (coastal and riverine floods) for different climate change scenarios (e.g. RCP4.5 and RCP8.5). All the tools mentioned are open-source, to ensure widespread adoption, and are the current state of the art in climate hazard modelling.

Traditional climate models often struggle to capture localized urban hazards due to their limited spatial resolution (and lack of explicit hydrological and hydraulic components), making adaptation strategies less effective. The tools developed in the SCORE project address this challenge by refining large-scale climate data into high-resolution datasets. This allows for the development of flood projection models that not only reflect the specific characteristics of each coastal city, but also incorporate key inputs such as river discharge, sea-level rise, and extreme weather events, each modelled taking into account the specific urban settings. Additionally, the high-resolution flood maps generated from these refined datasets provide valuable support to local policymakers, helping them design evidence-based adaptation strategies tailored to the unique challenges of each urban environment.

Long-term coastal erosion analysis

Coastal erosion is a major challenge for urban resilience planning. Developing high-resolution tools to model shoreline evolution is essential to improve disaster preparedness and to support more informed urban planning to mitigate long-term climate change risks. The SCORE project has developed an innovative package of methodologies and models for downscaling climate data and evaluating long-term shoreline evolution. These models use large-scale climate outputs, available through open and reliable European data services, to produce high resolution and localized data. This process is essential for urban applications bridging the gap between global and regional climate models (GCMs and RCMs, which have a resolution of tens of kilometers) and the detailed data needed for the development of coastal erosion projection models, that reflect the specific characteristics of the area of interest. The hazard evaluation tools developed during the project integrate downscaled wave and sea-level rise models based on IPCC RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios, numerical models for coastal morphodynamics, such as the CoSMoS-COAST model, statistical tools for shoreline change projections, and remote sensing combined with GIS-based shoreline monitoring. These models enable evidence-based decision-making for coastal risk management and

adaptation strategies by providing comprehensive assessments of shoreline evolution, sediment transport, as well as erosion risks under different climate scenarios.

Traditional coastal planning approaches often fail to consider long-term erosion trends and climate-driven changes. The SCORE project addresses this gap by providing high-resolution models that predict shoreline retreat and sediment loss, and assess the impact of sea-level rise on urbanized coastlines.

Policy makers responsible for beach usage decisions could benefit from a long-term analysis in beach-use and management planning. The SCORE outputs can be directly utilized for this purpose for the cities involved. The scalability of these tools allows the entire methodology to be applied to others coastal areas. Finally, researchers can reuse the package or leverage the results obtained for further studies.

5.6.2. Recommendations at different levels

Local Level

Mandate High-Resolution Flood Hazard Mapping for Coastal Cities

- Local governments should require municipalities to create and update high-resolution flood hazard maps to enable proactive disaster management in different phases.
- SCORE Contribution: The project developed short-term hazard modeling tools and long-term coastline evolution models that refine climate projections for specific coastal locations, improving flood risk assessments. The finding highlights how flood risks and adaptation needs can vary significantly at the local scale, underscoring the importance of high-resolution modeling for urban resilience. (a) In Massa, Italy, future projections indicate an increased risk of flooding due to rising sea levels and increasing flood events. In this case, coastal flooding is virtually absent nowadays, but in future scenarios it will be of the same order of magnitude as riverine flooding, compromising much of the urban area. (b) In Oarsoaldea, Spain, results revealed an unexpected outcome; under the RCP4.5 scenario, riverine flood extents were greater than those projected under RCP8.5, challenging conventional assumptions and demonstrating the critical role of local-scale analysis. (c) In Vilanova, Spain, while coastal defenses effectively protect the city core, sandy beaches remain highly vulnerable, influencing long-term planning strategies. All the above cases illustrate a key lesson: flood dynamics and vulnerabilities cannot be generalized across regions, reinforcing the need for detailed urban-scale assessments to inform adaptation strategies.

Integrate Coastal Erosion Hazard Maps into Urban Planning

- Municipalities should mandate the use of high-resolution, long-term coastal evolution models in local urban planning, land-use regulations, and infrastructure development to minimize erosion risks in coastal zones.
- SCORE Contribution: The long-term coastline evolution models provide detailed projections of shoreline retreat and sediment transport, ensuring that local adaptation plans are data-driven and evidence-based. The SCORE project has developed an innovative package of methodologies and models for downscaling climate data and evaluating long-term shoreline evolution. The tools are freely available, reducing reliance on proprietary software and related costs and constraints. The methods can be adapted for diverse urban environments beyond SCORE target cities, but (a) running the high-resolution models requires advanced infrastructure (b) accuracy depends on high-quality historical and observational data (c) needs interdisciplinary expertise for proper interpretation.

Ensure open access to flood hazard and erosion maps

- Flood hazard maps erosion maps and risk models should be publicly accessible through municipal GIS platforms to enhance transparency and enable informed decision-making for land-use planning and disaster risk reduction.
- SCORE Contribution: The WP3 tools provide data-driven flood risk assessments that can be integrated into digital platforms for use by local authorities and emergency responders. In addition, the SCORE hazard evaluation tools enable visualization and projection of coastal erosion risks through GIS-based platforms, making data accessible for local adaptation planning. Remote sensing analysis in Sligo, Ireland, highlighted increasing erosion risks due to storm surge and sea-level rise, prompting early mitigation efforts.

Support Data-Driven Decision-Making for Beach and Sediment Management

- Local policymakers responsible for beach usage and management planning should utilize SCORE's shoreline evolution models to assess sediment transport, beach nourishment, and coastal defense effectiveness.
- SCORE Contribution: CoSMoS-COAST simulations in Benidorm helped assess beach nourishment strategies, optimizing coastal protection investments. Shoreline modeling in Massa Italy identified critical erosion hotspots, leading to targeted sediment management plans.

National Level

Establish National Standards for Hazard Mapping

- Governments should implement standardized methodologies for flood and erosion hazard mapping across all coastal municipalities, ensuring consistent and comparable risk assessments nationwide.
- SCORE Contribution: The long-term coastline evolution models offer a framework for standardized coastal risk assessments, ensuring that national policies are based on scientifically validated methodologies.

Expand Funding for Flood Hazard Mapping

- National authorities should provide dedicated funding programs for municipalities to adopt advanced flood modeling tools and improve local data collection on flood risks.
- SCORE Contribution: SCORE's short-term hazard evaluation tools ("D3.8 Short-term hazard modelling³²") demonstrated how detailed flood projections improve the accuracy of local risk assessments, justifying increased investment in high-resolution mapping efforts.

Enhance Funding for Erosion Hazard Monitoring

- National agencies should allocate dedicated funding to help municipalities and research institutions deploy high-resolution monitoring tools, ensuring long-term tracking of coastline evolution.
- SCORE Contribution: The high-resolution hazard evaluation tools demonstrate that continuous monitoring and model refinement are essential for accurate erosion risk assessments, justifying increased investment.

³² SCORE zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/score-eu-project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

EU Level

Integrate Advanced Flood Hazard Mapping into EU Climate Adaptation Policies

- The EU Floods Directive should mandate that Member States incorporate dynamic flood hazard models into their national and regional adaptation strategies to improve cross-border climate resilience.
- SCORE Contribution: SCORE's WP3 methodologies enhance traditional flood mapping by integrating coastal evolution modelling, providing a scientifically robust approach for adaptation planning.

Incorporate Advanced Coastal Erosion Models into EU Adaptation Strategies

- The EU Adaptation Strategy and Coastal Zone Management policies should integrate high-resolution, long-term coastal evolution models into climate resilience planning and funding programs.
- SCORE Contribution: The SCORE coastline evolution models enhance traditional coastal risk assessments by providing long-term projections that improve European coastal adaptation strategies.

5.7 IT Solutions

5.7.1 Description of outputs and tools

SCORE ICT Platform (<https://platform.score-eu-project.eu/#/>)

The SCORE ICT Platform (SIP - Smart Integrated Platform) is a centralized digital infrastructure developed in SCORE to support data acquisition, storage, and sharing for the project. It integrates sensor data, geospatial information, and project results into a unified system, enabling stakeholders to access and analyse environmental and climate-related data and thus, supporting adaptive decision-making and resilience planning.

SIP is structured around **three interconnected subsystems** that work together to support climate adaptation and environmental monitoring in coastal cities.

The **Data Hub** serves as the central repository for geospatial datasets and climate-related information. Built using GeoNode and GeoServer, it allows stakeholders to store, visualize, and analyze environmental data. This subsystem provides tools such as interactive GIS mapping, geostories, and dashboards, helping policymakers, researchers, and communities explore climate risks, adaptation strategies, and project outputs in a user-friendly format. By integrating data from multiple sources, the Data Hub supports evidence-based decision-making and enhances accessibility to critical climate information.

The **Sensor Service** is the real-time monitoring component of the SIP, designed to collect and process environmental data from institutional sensors, low-cost sensors, and citizen science initiatives. Built on the FROST Server, it ensures interoperability through OGC SensorThings API and Sensor Observation Service (SOS), allowing seamless data exchange between different monitoring systems. This subsystem enables coastal communities to track climate hazards, evaluate adaptation interventions, and improve risk assessment through continuous data streams.

The Knowledge Marketplace Platform acts as a collaborative knowledge-sharing environment within the SIP, allowing stakeholders to exchange data, best practices, and scientific insights on climate adaptation. Here is where the main project outcomes related to CCLL activities, including citizen science, participatory processes, co-design, and EBA solutions, will be available. It functions as a decision-support and networking tool, enabling users to contribute reports, share research findings, and participate in discussions about climate resilience. This platform ensures that knowledge generated by the SCORE project is accessible, practical, and directly applicable to policymakers, researchers, businesses, and local communities.

Building the SIP was particularly challenging, primarily due to the integration of numerous and diverse sensors. The process was often hindered by a lack of information regarding the devices' technical specifications, supported protocols, ownership, and authorization procedures.

Digital Twin Platform

The SCORE Digital Twin Platform is a GIS-based simulation tool designed to create virtual models of European coastal cities to assess climate risks and adaptation strategies. This platform integrates real-world environmental data, geospatial models, and predictive simulations to visualize, test, and optimize climate adaptation solutions, particularly those related to EBA.

The platform is composed of two key modules:

- **User Scenario Evaluation (USE) Module** – Allows users to simulate what-if scenarios, evaluating the impact of different adaptation strategies on urban areas. Users can define variables such as weather events, sea-state conditions, and EBA implementations to assess potential flooding and economic impacts.
- **Early-Warning Support (EWS) Module** – Runs real-time monitoring and forecasting simulations, continuously analyzing environmental data from sensors and weather models to detect flooding risks and extreme weather threats.

This digital environment allows policymakers, urban planners, and emergency responders to evaluate different adaptation measures before implementation, enhancing climate resilience planning.

User scenario evaluation

The User Scenario Evaluation module is a core function of the Digital Twin Platform, enabling users to simulate climate risks and adaptation strategies. It can be employed for running simulations enabling what-if and long-term analyses on scenarios built by users as a mixture of real, ground-truth data from a coastal city, and hypothetical data, e.g. regarding weather events, sea state, and solutions based on EBAs implemented within the urban study area.

It can address the need of policymakers, administrators, and environmental management entities of making predictions on the impact of the climate change and possible countermeasures on sustainable urban planning.

The system is a powerful tool for simulating sudden and adverse weather events, which can be caused by climate change, and assessing their impact on an urban area, calculating damages due to subsequent floods to people, buildings and infrastructures. It also allows evaluating the mitigating impact of possible countermeasures, possibly based on EBAs, without actually implementing them. However, the system requires an initial effort by the users, since many input data must be provided: city digital surface models, data from sensors, land-use maps, possibly studies on vulnerability and exposures maps for people, buildings and infrastructures.

Meanwhile, the GIS-Based Early Warning System focuses on real-time monitoring and predictive hazard alerts. These two systems complement each other, ensuring that European coastal cities can both proactively plan for climate resilience and respond to immediate environmental risks.

GIS-Based Early Warning System

The Early-Warning Support (EWS) module of the SCORE Digital Twin Platform is an AI-powered monitoring and alert system that continuously tracks and predicts extreme weather events such as coastal flooding, storm surges, and heavy rainfall-induced river overflows. It operates autonomously, leveraging real-time environmental data from distributed sensor networks and weather forecasts to assess potential risks and generate timely alerts.

Designed as a decision-support tool for urban planners, civil protection agencies, and environmental managers, the system processes sensor data, evaluates flood risks, and raises alerts when predicted water levels threaten human safety, infrastructure, and economic assets. The integration of machine learning and predictive analytics enhances its capability to forecast short-term climate risks, enabling authorities to implement proactive disaster management strategies.

Unlike traditional monitoring systems, the EWS module runs continuously without requiring manual input, ensuring real-time assessment of changing environmental conditions. However, its effectiveness depends on the availability

of high-quality input data, such as city digital surface models, sensor readings, land-use maps, and vulnerability studies. Once operational, the system provides accurate flood risk assessments, allowing cities to optimize early-warning responses, protect citizens, and minimize economic damage from extreme weather events.

5.7.2. Recommendations at different levels

Local level

Leverage Open Data Platforms for Climate-Informed Urban Planning and Monitoring

- Local governments should adopt open, interoperable data platforms to support climate-resilient urban planning and integrate local environmental monitoring systems with European data standards. These platforms should enable the collection, visualization, and sharing of real-time and historical data (covering climate risks, environmental quality, and EBA outcomes) to inform transparent, inclusive, and evidence-based decision-making.
- **SCORE Contribution:** The SCORE ICT Platform (accessible at platform.score-eu-project.eu) integrates geospatial data, low-cost sensor feeds, and citizen science inputs into an open-access, GIS-based environment. It supports urban planners through scenario visualizations, climate risk layers, and real-time monitoring tools, including the Digital Twin and Early Warning modules. The platform's API Middleware enables seamless integration of heterogeneous data sources, compliant with OGC SensorThings API and Sensor Observation Services, allowing interoperability with Copernicus, INSPIRE, and other EU-level services. Moreover, the platform has been used within SCORE's CCLLs to assess and promote the effectiveness of EBA measures and influence local policy and planning processes.

Enable Citizen Participation through Digital Platforms

- Cities should use digital tools like SCORE's ICT platform to support citizen science and participatory monitoring, empowering residents to contribute to urban resilience and adaptation strategies. The platform can also be used to communicate actionable insights to stakeholders, including schools, citizens, and businesses and inspire behavioural change.
- **SCORE Contribution:** The platform hosts community-contributed datasets, allows geosurvey creation, and supports data uploads from low-cost sensors used by citizens, thus operationalizing citizen engagement in real-time urban monitoring. Also, the SCORE GeoStories (<https://platform.score-eu-project.eu/catalogue/#/?f=geostory>) serve as a key visualization element within the SCORE ICT network. Each CCLL has its own GeoStory, showcasing the actions implemented in the city and the corresponding results in enhancing resilience against coastal erosion and extreme weather events caused by climate change. This powerful tool plays a crucial role in fostering public engagement.

Integrate Digital Twin simulation into urban planning

- City administrations should integrate Digital Twin simulations into their urban planning and climate adaptation workflows. Local authorities and technical departments should use the DT to visualize hazard exposure (especially flood risk and coastal erosion), test nature-based solutions (like EBAs), and involve citizens in co-creating resilient urban strategies.
- **SCORE Contribution:** The SCORE Digital Twin simulates flood scenarios and shoreline evolution using downscaled climate projections and real-time data, as demonstrated in cities like Massa and Dublin ("D8.8

GIS Based Early Warning and Digital Twin Platform integration report³³), enabling city planners and technical staff to visualize the impact of climate hazards and test adaptation strategies before implementation.

National Level

Enable Scaling and Institutional Support

- Use the SCORE ICT platform as a national tool to consolidate environmental monitoring data from diverse regions, enabling comprehensive analysis and reporting. Although the platform is local in use, it benefits from centralized coordination, particularly in terms of sensor standardization, data quality assurance, and capacity building.
- SCORE Contribution: The platform's architecture is built on open standards (OGC SensorThings API, SOS) and uses modular design to allow expansion. This makes it suitable for national adaptation initiatives and replicable in various city contexts.

Adoption of interoperable Digital Twin platforms

- National and regional authorities should promote the adoption of interoperable Digital Twin platforms to support regional adaptation planning and emergency response. This includes issuing technical guidelines, funding integration in regional climate risk platforms, and training programs for public agencies.
- SCORE Contribution: SCORE's Digital Twin and Early Warning System (DT-EWS) provide real-time hazard modelling and scenario-based simulations adaptable to different regional contexts ("D8.10 Early warning and spatial digital twin Assessment Plan³⁴"). It is built on interoperable data standards, making it suitable for integration into broader national climate resilience strategies.

EU Level

Promote Interoperability and Data Sharing Across Borders

- EU could recognize and promote platforms like SCORE as models of best practice for implementing the EU Digital Strategy, INSPIRE Directive, Flood Directive, Biodiversity Strategy and the EU Climate Adaptation Strategy. SCORE-like platforms should also be encouraged under EU Missions and co-funded regional initiatives. Supporting interoperability across Member States enables cross-border data exchange, especially in shared climate risk regions (e.g. river basins, coastal zones).
- SCORE Contribution: The ICT Platform links local environmental data with broader European datasets, such as those from Copernicus and Open Data Portals, aligning with EU-level data governance and environmental monitoring goals.

Promotion of Digital Twin

- The European Commission should support Digital Twin technologies as scalable, open-access tools for local adaptation. Funding programs should encourage Digital Twin deployment in vulnerable regions and cross-border coastal zones.

³³ <https://zenodo.org/records/11242933>

³⁴ Confidential report

- **SCORE Contribution:** The SCORE DT platform is scalable, open-source, and built on standard APIs. It supports the EU Adaptation Strategy by translating complex climate data into actionable local information and can be linked with Copernicus and INSPIRE data services for pan-European use.

5.8 Educational, Communicational, and Capacity-Building Tools

5.8.1 Description of outputs and tools

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC) (<https://score.thinkific.com/>)

A Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) is an open-online course for which participants from around the world can learn about a specific topic, utilising a variety of mediums, including videos, user forums, quizzes, reading materials, links to external supplementary materials and much more. MOOCs provide an affordable and flexible way to learn new skills and deliver quality educational experiences at scale. The utilisation of SCORE's MOOCs enables the project to reach a wider audience and provide valuable climate action skills/learnings to citizens in Europe and worldwide.

The MOOC is a useful tool that could be used to inform policymakers, or the general public, about a specific topic. For SCORE, there are currently 5 different courses across a variety of user levels, focusing on community engagement, EBA implementation, coastal monitoring, participatory approaches and the CCLL concept in practice.

In developing each course, the key stakeholders' needs are considered to ensure that the modules created are tailored more appropriately to the intended audience. This in turn allows courses to maximise both generated interest and overall impact.

CORE CCLL stakeholders: The CCLL stakeholders have an intense learning curve when participating in the project, and MOOCs can help empower them to feel engaged in this process by gaining more background information on what SCORE is doing and why. By fostering this education, the MOOC can enable the local stakeholders to continue implementing the SCORE approach beyond the project's end date.

Local municipalities & practitioners: In local areas with an interest in increasing resilience to climate change, the MOOCs can provide practitioners and policymakers an opportunity to understand how SCORE approaches can be applied within their context, the materials and skillsets needed to implement, and the opportunities for change when applied. Further, introductory courses can provide these individuals with a simple, accessible way to gain the scientific and methodological background necessary to understand the proposed climate and community-based solutions.

Students & Teachers: Developed MOOCs will allow students to educate themselves on a variety of relevant topics such as Nature-Based Solutions, co-creation and co-design, the development of living labs, and the role of technology in community engagement. A MOOC can achieve this through both theory and practical examples to provide a comprehensive understanding of key concepts, while highlighting the work done through the SCORE project. MOOCs can be a unique way for a student to engage more creatively with scientific content, making the courses a great addition for any teacher to add to their curriculum as primary or supplementary material.

Living Labs in other EU-funded projects: Building competencies with the terminology and framework used in establishing a living lab takes a significant amount of time for stakeholders unfamiliar with the process. External EU projects establishing living labs and EBA/NbS could use these resources to allow their respective stakeholders the opportunity to learn about these concepts in the early stages of the project, thereby fostering a more productive living lab engagement process.

Citizens/General Public: For anyone interested in the SCORE approach, specifically Nature-Based Solutions, citizen science and climate change, the MOOCs will provide them with an introduction to these concepts, and if interested, they can continue to the more challenging modules to upskill in these areas. As such, the MOOCs are an excellent tool to engage with individuals that might not otherwise have access to educational materials on these subjects.

There are over 1,200 enrolments to the courses. However, a majority of the SCORE MOOC is only available in English, which may pose a barrier for some coastal cities.

Other communication tools

The MOOCs have been developed in conjunction with SCORE's yearly EBA Training Schools to provide attendees with the necessary background, resources, and links to participate in the activities. Additionally, webinars run during the EBA Training Schools have been incorporated into relevant MOOCs.

SCORE also prepared and ran EBAcraft (a custom game in Minecraft, see links in the resources) game sessions to engage young participants in designing environmentally friendly ways to protect their homes and improve coastal cities for the future. Players were tasked with working collaboratively to address threats to a fictional coastal city using EBAs. The game needs to be set up and the resources will help set up the custom game. UCD is working on a MOOC for both geodesign game and EBA Craft to be ready in June.

To further promote environmental awareness among younger audiences, SCORE developed engaging kids' activities such as a draw-your-own-sand-dune worksheet (https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/SCORE_kidsgames.pdf), which educates children about the importance of dunes in protecting coastal areas. In addition, a SCORE-themed board game (<https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/SCORE-Board-Game.pdf>) was designed, allowing players to simulate actions across the 10 CCLs and experience the outcomes of both nature-based and unsustainable decisions in a fun, interactive format.

5.8.2. Recommendations at different levels

Local Level

Enhance capacity of local actors

- Municipalities can organize training sessions and workshops to enhance the capacity of local actors.
- SCORE Contribution: SCORE has developed Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) to enhance awareness of flood and erosion risks, promote EBA solutions, and support the creation of Urban Living Labs. These courses also introduce Citizen Science approaches, foster community engagement, and encourage youth participation through EBAcraft (a custom game in Minecraft) for climate action. Additionally, they provide training on SCORE tools, including the ICT platform for climate adaptation and the use of digital twins in urban flood risk management.

National Level

National Training modules

- National education and environment agencies can incorporate digital education tools and citizen engagement formats (like those piloted in SCORE) into official climate education and awareness programs.
- SCORE Contribution: SCORE's MOOCs and EBA training schools provided structured content accessible to diverse audiences. These scalable formats can support national adaptation curricula and training for civil servants or technical staff.

EU Level

Upskill stakeholders across Member States

- The EU should promote the adoption of innovative and accessible communication tools (e.g. gamified learning, open MOOCs, creative workshops) in funded climate adaptation projects and education programs, ensuring greater inclusivity and knowledge transfer.
- SCORE Contribution: SCORE's publicly available resources and MOOCs hosted on open platforms ensure continuity of learning beyond the project lifecycle. These tools can serve as best practices for other Horizon Europe projects and EU Missions on Adaptation.

6. SYSTEMIC ADOPTION OF LIVING LABS

Ensure broad recognition of Living Labs (LLs) as permanent, systemic initiatives is crucial for maximizing their potential within European policy frameworks³⁵.

While many Directorates-General (DGs) of the European Commission recognize the importance of stable, open innovation ecosystems for experimentation and piloting - such as those in the *A Soil Deal for Europe Mission*³⁶, *Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities Mission*³⁷, and *Cancer Mission*³⁸ - a key challenge remains. Many initiatives that claim to be Living Labs are in fact project-based, applying the methodology to specific, time-bound challenges rather than embedding it at a macro level as permanent, systemic initiatives. As project-based Living Labs, they often receive funding and support with limited to short-term funding cycles, which can constrain their long-term impact. To achieve sustained results, these initiatives should be recognized as permanent fixtures within the innovation ecosystem.

ENoLL's recent policy recommendations³⁹ stress the importance of embedding Living Labs in long-term frameworks, highlighting their role as critical actors in the Green and Digital Transitions, and emphasizing the need to integrate them into EU-funded projects as key collaborators in co-creation and user-centric innovation. By ensuring that Living Labs are recognized as neutral orchestrators within stable ecosystems, they can provide real, lasting impact by building trust among stakeholders and ensuring the continuity needed for tackling complex, ongoing challenges.

Support the definition of practical strategies to ensure the long-term sustainability of LLs, particularly in addressing wicked problems that require adaptive, iterative solutions.

Moreover, there is a pressing need for practical strategies to ensure the long-term sustainability of Living Labs, particularly in addressing wicked problems that require adaptive, iterative solutions. Living Labs, with their user-driven, co-creation approach, offer a unique platform for addressing these challenges. They facilitate the development of solutions that are not only relevant to the contexts they are applied but also scalable across different contexts, ensuring that short-term innovations can lead to long-term, transformative change. This distinction between temporary, project-based and permanent Living Labs is crucial for fostering a deeper understanding of how best to support them at various scales, ensuring their potential is fully realized in both short-term and long-term contexts.

Recognise and support LLs as permanent, systemic initiatives

Coastal cities could benefit from the creation or use of proper Living Labs to support the experimentation of new systems and technologies to face the challenges posed by Climate Change. Only permanent structures, which can experiment with different solutions over time and adapt quickly to emerging needs without having to restart the engagement process from scratch - could deploy the full potential of the Living Labs.

³⁵ According to ENoLL definition: "Living Labs are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments based on a systematic user co-creation approach that integrates research and innovation activities in communities and/or multi-stakeholder environments, placing citizens and/or end-users at the centre of the innovation process". ENoLL (2025). Living Lab origins, developments and future perspectives. Published by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), 2025 [D. Schuurman, M.I. DeLosRios-White, M. Desole (eds)]. Licensed under CC BY-NC 4.0. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14764597>.

³⁶ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/soil-deal-europe_en

³⁷ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/knowledge-publications-tools-and-data/publications/all-publications/100-climate-neutral-cities-2030-and-citizens_en

³⁸ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/eu-mission-cancer_en

³⁹ ENoLL (2025). Policy Recommendations for Integrating Living Labs in Framework Programme 10. <https://enoll.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Policy-Recommendations-for-Integrating-Living-Labs-in-FP10.pdf>

Several EU Missions and Horizon Europe Clusters, such as those focused on *climate resilience*, *energy transition*, *smart cities*, and *regional innovation*, face policy gaps that Living Labs are uniquely positioned to help address. For instance, the *Adaptation to Climate Change Mission* requires extensive stakeholder engagement and the development of locally tailored, scalable solutions. Living Labs excel in engaging diverse stakeholders - governments, businesses, communities, and academia - ensuring that climate adaptation strategies are co-created and deeply rooted in local contexts. Similarly, in the *Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities Mission*, Living Labs can play a pivotal role in testing and implementing innovative urban solutions, bridging the gap between high-level policy goals and the real-world application of sustainable technologies. Furthermore, in the *Restore our Ocean and Waters Mission*, Living Labs can facilitate the testing of eco-innovations and water management systems in real-world settings, accelerating the transition to a circular economy.

By providing a space for experimentation, iteration, and collaboration, Living Labs can address the policy gap of ensuring that these complex, long-term missions are not just ambitious visions, but actionable, sustainable solutions. In addition, Living Labs can support the development of inclusive governance models that promote social inclusion and equitable participation, ensuring that all stakeholders, particularly those from underserved communities - are involved in the design and implementation of solutions.

By recognizing and supporting Living Labs as permanent, systemic initiatives, EU policies can harness their full potential, creating a collaborative, adaptive, and resilient innovation ecosystem. This approach will not only address immediate policy gaps but also pave the way for sustainable, community-driven solutions that are vital for achieving the EU's long-term climate, environmental, and social goals.

7. COMPLEMENTARITIES OF SCORE WITH ECFAS

The SCORE project and the European Coastal Flood Awareness System (ECFAS⁴⁰) represent two important European efforts to address the growing threat of coastal flooding and climate-related hazards. While both share a focus on addressing challenges posed by climate change and coastal risks, contributing with valuable tools and insights to the field of climate resilience, they differ in scope, approach, and application.

Some project objectives and the clustering approach can be found both in ECFAS and SCORE, enhancing decision-making through tools that simulate flood scenarios and assess the socio-economic impacts of flooding. However, SCORE addresses a broader set of climate resilience issues, including sea level rise, coastal erosion, and ecosystem health, whereas ECFAS narrows its focus to coastal flood awareness and related risk management.

ECFAS, developed in collaboration with the European Commission and the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), is a **continental-scale system** that provides flood monitoring and forecasting across Europe. As part of the Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS), its strength lies in its ability to deliver early warning information (such as probabilistic medium-range flood predictions, flash flood indicators, and impact projections) across national borders. Designed to support emergency response coordination and improve transnational flood preparedness, ECFAS serves as a high-level operational service that complements national efforts, especially in large river basins and coastal zones.

In contrast, the SCORE project operates at a fundamentally different level. Rather than applying a top-down, uniform model across the continent, **SCORE focuses on place-based resilience**, developing high-resolution, community-driven solutions through the establishment of ten CCLs in diverse pilot cities across Europe. These Living Labs act as experimental innovation ecosystems, co-developed with local stakeholders to create tailored adaptation strategies that are context-specific, socially inclusive, and environmentally sustainable. This “boots-on-the-ground” kind of approach is on purpose tailored for small spatial and time scales and high-resolution solutions, that are close to citizens and to the needs of local administrations. Indeed, the SCORE EWS supports local/regional institutions in charge at different administration levels for emergency management. These are supported to take prompt actions especially in the case of flash floods, which are fast-evolving events for which satellite observations can be unavailable due to the revisiting time, or insufficient image quality during precipitation due to cloud coverage.

A defining innovation of SCORE lies in its integration of Digital Twin technology, which allows participating cities to create virtual representations of their urban and coastal environments. These dynamic models enable stakeholders to simulate climate scenarios, test EBAs, and assess socio-economic impacts in a virtual space before implementing them in the real world. This approach ensures greater relevance, feasibility, and public support for adaptation interventions.

Moreover, SCORE emphasises the role of EBA as cost-effective, scalable alternatives to hard engineering. Through active community engagement and participatory co-creation processes, these interventions not only address physical vulnerabilities but also foster awareness, behavioural change, and a stronger sense of ownership among local populations.

⁴⁰ <https://www.ecfas.eu/>

Whereas ECFAS primarily supports macro-scale flood awareness and risk modelling at the European level, SCORE excels in ground-level innovation, offering advantages that are especially critical for integrated urban planning and participatory governance. Its methodologies are not only replicable across different regions, but are also highly adaptable, making SCORE an effective tool for municipalities seeking to operationalise the EU Climate Adaptation Strategy, the Flood Directive, and Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM) practices.

In summary, while ECFAS provides valuable early warning infrastructure and regional coordination capacity, the SCORE project stands out for its localised impact, policy relevance, and holistic innovation framework. By combining Digital Twin systems, EBA, and citizen science within Living Labs, SCORE delivers a robust, replicable model of climate resilience that is deeply rooted in the realities and aspirations of coastal communities. It can be considered a strategic complement or even a necessary counterpart to broader European systems like ECFAS, bridging the gap between continental forecasting and local action.

8. FEW SUCCESS STORIES FROM CCLLS

ADAPTATION MEASURES

This section showcases a few success stories in climate adaptation from the SCORE's CCLLs, illustrating the practical application of project tools and their relevance for policy making. The referenced case studies offer concrete examples of how targeted adaptation measures have enhanced local resilience to climate-related challenges. For a comprehensive account of these experiences and lessons learned, please refer to Deliverable “D2.4 Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs⁴¹”.

Oarsoaldea CCLL (Spain)

From the beginning of the project, Oarsoaldea developed a strategic plan based on the “Pilot Operational Plan”. Its main objective was to balance the internal development of the CCLL and to strengthen the commitment and participation of the different stakeholders.

As a regional public entity, its main target was to raise awareness of the need to adapt to climate change and to promote the use of NbSs, both among citizens and the local authorities it represents. To achieve this, it was essential to deliver a clear and convincing message that would effectively reach all stakeholders. In this context, the implementation of demonstrative NbS/EBAs in each of the four municipalities (with a multiplier impact by mobilising a larger budget than that provided by SCORE), participatory activities and the development of the Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) have been key to achieve this objective. In turn, the CBA has allowed synthesising and connecting the results of the flood, damage and economic loss models, highlighting the value of NbS for damage avoidance, also from an economic perspective.

Another priority during the development of the technical results was to strengthen the connection with citizens through concrete actions, such as the installation of sensors and the organisation of participatory events. These activities enabled the initiation of new community practices and generated greater collective awareness.

Piran CCLL (Slovenia)

Piran applied **ecosystem-based adaptation** approaches, including the use of green infrastructure and natural buffers, supported by **stakeholder assessments**. This CCLL emphasized co-creation with citizens, municipal staff, and environmental experts to integrate ecological knowledge into urban planning. A strong focus was placed on aligning adaptation measures with environmental protection and sustainable tourism.

Sligo CCLL (Ireland)

Sligo developed **flood mapping tools** combining citizen-contributed data and sensor measurements. The CCLL engaged local communities and schools in data collection and map validation processes, raising awareness and improving risk communication. These tools informed emergency planning and enhanced preparedness at the municipal level.

Vilanova i la Geltrú CCLL (Spain)

Vilanova focused on **financial risk profiles** that provide a detailed understanding of potential financial losses from flooding and the **use of the Decision Support System** (DSS) to simulate financial strategies and assess trade-offs between different approaches to risk mitigation. Vilanova i la Geltrú CCLL, kicked off these activities by collating all

⁴¹ SCORE zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/score-eu-project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

the necessary data needed to shape the exposure models. Co-creation sessions with municipal representatives emphasized the importance of visualising financial impacts in an accessible format, leading to refinements in the accessibility and usability of the Decision Support System. Further, the EBAs incorporated into the risk profiles were selected during further co-creation sessions with local stakeholders, ensuring that solutions reflected regional priorities and constraints.

Massa CCLL (Italy)

Massa developed a **Digital Twin prototype** to simulate flood events and assess vulnerabilities in real time. By integrating meteorological and hydrological data with urban infrastructure models, the tool supports **data-driven decision-making** and future adaptation planning. It enabled scenario testing and visualizations that help local authorities prioritize investments in flood mitigation.

Dublin CCLL (Ireland)

In Dublin's CCLL, digital tools are being explored to support local climate adaptation efforts. The SCORE Sensor Map, developed by the team, has helped local authorities begin to visualize real-time environmental data, contributing to more responsive decision-making. Building on this, XR (Extended Reality) data visualization tools are currently being tested to explore how 3D and immersive formats might offer more intuitive ways of understanding and communicating climate data. These developments reflect the ongoing effort to translate project tools into practical support for local resilience planning.

Meanwhile, the SCORE Geosurveys platform is currently active and running as a citizen-led climate monitoring and engagement tool.

Oeiras CCLL (Portugal)

Oeiras implemented a wide **deployment of environmental sensors** to monitor rainfall, humidity, and temperature in real time. The data informed both local authorities and citizens through accessible dashboards. The initiative demonstrated how **low-cost sensor networks**, co-designed with local stakeholders, can support real-time monitoring and adaptive decision-making in coastal cities.

Gdańsk CCLL (Poland)

Gdańsk conducted a detailed analysis of historical urban flash floods and extreme torrential rain events. This work initiated a Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA), which highlighted the need to prioritize EBAs. Subsequently, the MCA supported efforts to promote and implement these solutions within the city. These outcomes, among others, have been further developed through the implementation of the Horizon Europe Pro-Climate project. New projects, such as those led by Sligo and Gdańsk CCLLs contribute to ensuring continuity and securing additional funding to support long-term sustainability.

Samsun CCLL (Turkey)

The Samsun CCLL stands out with its integrated approach to flood risk management in the Kızılırmak Delta and Bafra Plain-areas highly vulnerable to climate change impacts. Through participatory mapping, hydrological modeling (HEC-RAS 2D), and collaboration with local authorities, schools, and citizens, the CCLL has developed community-based adaptation strategies. A notable achievement is the integration of citizen science and green infrastructure solutions, such as co-designed tree planting activities in flood-prone zones, which not only raised

public awareness but also contributed to long-term resilience. These initiatives have informed local development planning and enhanced institutional learning on NbS.

Samsun CCLL also plays a key role in Türkiye's national Living Lab ecosystem. It benefits from the experience and technical know-how of Başakşehir Living Lab, one of the country's most established Living Labs, through active knowledge exchange. Simultaneously, Samsun CCLL provides mentorship and support to the newly established Sinop Living Lab, helping build its capacity for early-stage climate adaptation.

Benidorm CCLL (Spain)

Benidorm focused on developing studies on the evolution of coastal erosion, climate change, and the future shoreline projection using the CoSMoS COAST model. Based on this, beach nourishment strategies were proposed in collaboration with the City Council, some of which will be implemented in the coming years. Stakeholder workshops were a key pillar to ensure successful decision-making.

More stories

Sensors' selection

The selection of sensors across the Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) was a collaborative and iterative process, with each CCLL actively involved in identifying the key environmental parameters to monitor. Using this valuable input, the WP4 team shortlisted appropriate sensors and developed the SCORE Sensor Catalogue. Although the initial catalogue had limitations, particularly in regional coverage and the availability of locally relevant sensors, the WP4 team addressed these challenges by continuously expanding and adapting the catalogue through ongoing stakeholder engagement and feedback. This ensured that each CCLL could select sensors tailored to their unique environmental and climatic contexts. By working closely with local stakeholders, the CCLLs successfully used the enhanced catalogue to choose and deploy sensors that met both technical standards and community needs.

Public Perceptions of Climate Risks, Vulnerability, and Adaptation Strategies: Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping in Irish and Spanish Living Labs.

As Europe faces 'extremely high' climate risks, being the fastest warming continent on the planet, it is crucial to invest in effective climate adaptation strategies to protect vulnerable communities. Despite this, limited studies have explored the effects of climate hazards on human lives, due to the assumption that European countries have sufficient adaptive capacity and socioeconomic resources. This has hindered policymaking, as lack of data fosters uncertainty and inefficiency. This study aims to address this research gap by exploring the public perceptions of climate change in two living lab regions in Europe, namely, in Spain and Ireland. This involves using qualitative tools like surveys and interviews to collate information on the impacts of climate change on communities, studying beliefs pertaining to climate hazards and how they shape behaviours. A key objective of the study is to determine the socioeconomic vulnerability of the populations in two diverse European regions, and similar trends were found. The study also assesses the role of policymaking in building adaptive capacity, gathering local insights and exploring the role of novel NbS in building resilience. Finally, this research uses fuzzy cognitive mapping to illustrate these complex processes and societal dynamics as part of a comprehensive systems analysis. Contrary to popular opinion, it is found that communities in Spanish and Irish regions are increasingly climate vulnerable. This study finds a relationship between experience of climate hazards and public willingness to engage in climate action, which is however, hindered by lack of effective citizen engagement policies. The increasing popularity of NbS due to their socioeconomic co-benefits is also highlighted, as is the need to contextualise adaptation strategies in local needs.

Ultimately, this study offers policymakers insights on trends found between two culturally and socioeconomically diverse European regions, based in systems analysis.

Assessment framework for ecosystem-based adaptation implementation at local level: insights from case studies in the Iberian Peninsula.

Climate hazard events, such as floods and heatwaves, are becoming more frequent and severe. This paper focuses on coastal urban areas and addresses the need for implementing effective EBA measures. It highlights the importance of integrating EBA into urban planning to enhance resilience. The study proposes a comprehensive assessment framework to guide EBA implementation process at the local level. Governance system, policy framework, and funding sources are identified as key factors influencing the process. Within governance structures, the study focuses on cooperation, decision-making processes, scientific knowledge, and political support. Plans and strategies, regulations, international treaties, or agreements are recognized within policy sphere. The framework also considers the importance of sustainable funding mechanisms, including Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) and fiscal incentives, to ensure the long-term viability of EBA interventions. The framework's applicability and effectiveness are tested by assessing ten implementation experiences in Spain and Portugal. The assessment underscores the need for adaptive governance and the inclusion of diverse stakeholders in planning and execution. The research concludes with the need for a systemic approach to integrating EBA into local adaptation strategies, to bridge the knowledge gap between researchers and practitioners, foster adaptation in coastal urban environments, and increase climate resilience.

9. BUSINESS OPPORTUNITIES

The SCORE policy recommendations that have been presented place particular emphasis on enhancing business opportunities within the EU, especially through (a) the promotion of EBA measures as effective solutions for coastal adaptation to climate change and (b) the uptake of tools developed during the project.

Enhanced Market Uptake of EBA

The SCORE project has demonstrated that EBA strategies are not only environmentally sound and socially accepted but also present a growing opportunity for market uptake and innovation. Through its network of ten CCLs, SCORE facilitated the co-design, evaluation, and prioritisation of EBA measures, such as dune restoration, rainwater harvesting systems, vegetated swales, and permeable pavements, tailored to local climate risks and stakeholder needs. MCA and CBA in SCORE demonstrated that EBA have the potential to be an economically efficient approach, while also offering additional co-benefits that may not be achievable through engineering-based solutions.

This real-world testing and stakeholder validation have strengthened the business case for EBAs, creating conditions for broader market deployment. By demonstrating their multifunctionality (i.e. enhancing flood protection, improving urban aesthetics, increasing biodiversity etc.) SCORE helped position EBAs as investable solutions for municipalities, developers, and service providers. Local companies involved in landscaping, environmental engineering, data analytics, and citizen science are increasingly able to align their services with the rising demand for climate-resilient infrastructure.

Unlocking Business Opportunities through SCORE Tools and Innovations

The SCORE project brought a new wave of business opportunities by developing a suite of interoperable tools that support climate adaptation in coastal cities. These tools span multiple domains, ranging from data services and citizen science to financial risk analysis and digital simulation, and are designed not only for public use but also for uptake by private actors, SMEs, and innovation ecosystems. The next step is to increase the validity and useability of these tools through new Research & Development activities to reach fully "market-ready climate resilience services".

The ICT platform, Digital Twin systems, and sensor networks could then present ~~direct~~ opportunities for tech developers, data service providers, and urban planners to offer tailored climate services to municipalities and infrastructure operators. Companies specialising in environmental analytics, early warning systems, and spatial modelling can build upon SCORE's open-access platforms to deliver location-specific insights, enhance risk preparedness, and inform investment planning.

On the other hand, the Co-Creation Toolkit, Citizen Science Playbook, and training materials equip consulting firms, educational institutions, and community-based enterprises with replicable methodologies for stakeholder engagement, environmental education, and participatory planning, thus enabling them to scale these services across other urban and regional contexts.

SCORE's outputs have laid a foundation for the development of climate resilience services, with clear pathways for public-private collaboration, procurement innovation, and capacity-building partnerships.

10. OTHER SCORE POLICY GUIDELINES

Seven policy briefs have been published by the SCORE consortium since the start of the project: 4 relevant at the European level and 3 targeting local policy-makers in two CCLs (Sligo and Oeiras). These are available for download on the SCORE website: <https://score-eu-project.eu/other-publications>. All policy briefs are promoted online and disseminated widely through the SCORE newsletter, by project partners to their networks, at events and through other EU projects. However, European and local policy briefs have different dissemination targets:

Policy briefs relevant at the European level, which are jointly developed with other EU projects or international initiatives, are widely distributed through these projects networks and presented at relevant events. For example, the “When will a 2-meter rise in sea level occur, and how might we adapt?” policy brief was presented at the COP27 in November 2022, and the [Nature-Based solutions for Resilient Coastal Cities](#) policy brief, developed by the Ocean & Climate Platform, has been distributed through the platform members (more than 100 members including research institutes, NGOs, aquariums, private sector, French institutions and international agencies and authorities).

Local policy briefs, having a prominent focus on the local level through the CCLs, are targeting in particular local policy makers. As an example, the policy brief relevant for Sligo was presented to the Sligo County Council and the project is now featured in the Climate Action Plan for Sligo: [sligococo.ie/Environment/ClimateAction/SCClimateActionPlan2024-2029/SCC Final LACAP.pdf](https://sligococo.ie/Environment/ClimateAction/SCClimateActionPlan2024-2029/SCC%20Final%20LACAP.pdf)

11. FOLLOW-UP ACTION PLAN

To ensure the long-term impact of the SCORE project, the following steps are suggested for policymakers based on scenario-based insights developed through SCORE's Digital Twins, hazard maps, socio-economic assessments, and risk projections. These steps are designed in constructive alignment with SCORE's core objectives: enhancing coastal resilience, promoting EBA, advancing citizen science, and supporting data-informed decision-making.

Local and Regional Authorities are encouraged to integrate SCORE's outputs, such as risk maps, financial resilience tools, and citizen science data, into spatial planning, civil protection, and climate adaptation strategies. For example, Digital Twin simulations developed in cities like Massa and Sligo can directly inform flood zoning, emergency response protocols, and investment priorities for EBA.

National Policymakers should scale up validated EBA interventions by incorporating them into coastal management and land-use policies. Tools like the EBA Catalogue and co-creation methodologies tested in CCLLs offer a replicable framework for engaging stakeholders and accelerating implementation.

At the **EU level**, institutions should leverage SCORE's ICT Platform and methodologies to complement existing services like Copernicus and implement priorities under the EU Adaptation Strategy and Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities. Alignment with the Floods Directive and the Nature Restoration Law offers further pathways for policy integration.

Moving forward, regular stakeholder engagement, capacity-building activities (e.g. MOOCs, training schools), and integration of SCORE tools into public procurement and funding mechanisms will ensure that policy recommendations evolve from guidance into action.

12. REFERENCES

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<https://unfccc.int/topics/adaptation-and-resilience/the-big-picture/introduction>

All SCORE deliverables and publications: <https://zenodo.org/communities/score-eu-project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

13. RESOURCES

CCLL framework

Image: <https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Living-Lab-Integrative-Process.pdf.png> Videos:

Introduction to the Living Lab integrative process: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dhNPNVsbacA>

Understanding the Living Lab integrative process: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XDIA5dxzKVw>

Living Lab integrative process – Empathize stage: Building a strong foundation:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xNSJk7pju6M>

Living Lab integrative process – Define stage: Identifying barriers and challenges:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rMyYolo5NfU>

Living Lab integrative process – Ideate stage: Co-designing creative solutions:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ov9jZk6Az0A>

Living Lab integrative process – Prototype stage: Bringing ideas to life:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=P2IySiYEwJE>

Living Lab integrative process – Test stage: Evaluating performance and impact:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BeP4t36N1m8>

Living Lab integrative process – Implement stage: Integrating solutions into real-world settings:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wwWbAupQN98>

Living Lab integrative process – Scale up stage: Expanding impact and reach:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zFyEiN9ItDE&t=1s>

Co-create your city toolbox

Page: <https://www.ihs.nl/en/advisory-training-and-research/tools-and-toolkits/co-create-your-city-toolkit>

Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CdYEPVWmXco&t=1s>

EBA catalogue

<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/6cbbb2f6ab0744b89dffda2664dd877e>

IT platform

<https://platform.score-eu-project.eu/#/>

Kids' activities

Draw-your-own-sand-dune worksheet: https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/SCORE_kidsgames.pdf

SCORE-themed board game: <https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/SCORE-Board-Game.pdf>

Monitoring and Evaluation

<https://www.ihs.nl/en/advisory-training-and-research/tools-and-toolkits>

MOOC

What are Nature-based solutions: <https://score.thinkific.com/courses/what-are-nature-based-solutions>

Ecosystem-based approaches: Introduction to implementation: <https://score.thinkific.com/courses/ecosystem-based-approaches>

Coastal monitoring for resilient communities: <https://score.thinkific.com/courses/coastal-monitoring>

SCORE deliverables and publications

Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/score-eu-project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Serious games (geodesign, EBACraft)

Geodesign Game resources:

Geodesign game: <https://score-eu-project.eu/geodesign-game/>

Geodesign game CCLL resources:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1IBTgslkO8800S60ma6Ea6dRA1Ak69Npp?usp=drive_link

EBACraft resources:

EBACraft Tutorial: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1FMbLrbW3-twJiBMxodweQSMFaxvMBhI9?usp=sharing>

EU Green Week 2023 YouTube Live: <https://youtube.com/live/6tp4u1vQ8EE?feature=share>

EBACraft at the Climate Adaptation Training School second edition YouTube Live: <https://youtube.com/live/hQL5JbIO4Yg?feature=share>

Serious games for Participatory planning: <https://score.thinkific.com/courses/serious-games>

SCORE website

<https://score-eu-project.eu/>

Pilot operational Plan

Video presentation of the POP template: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wF0KQhLqpVA>

Download the template: <https://score-eu-project.eu/tools-and-platforms/>

POP guidelines and instructions: <https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/Pilot-Operational-Plans.pdf>

